

Corpus compiled by Shanshan Lü (SHISU-ICSA) for the article:

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SINTIC

1. Standard Mandarin

Existential frame

(1) 怎么没有可口可乐呀?

zěnmě méi yǒu kěkǒukělè ya?

how NEG there.be Coca-Cola PRT

‘How come there wasn’t any Coca Cola?’

(Text, *School Camp*, line 79, Chappell)

- (2) 还有那种果味儿的蛋糕，
hái yǒu nèizhǒng guǒwèir de dāngāo
also there.be that.type fruit:flavoured DEATT cake
'There was also that kind of fruitcake.'
(Text, *School Camp*, line, 387, Chappell)

Possessive frame

- (3) 可口可乐就是没有那种瓶子，
kěkǒukělè jiùshi méi yǒu nèizhǒng píngzi
Coca-Cola indeed NEG have that.type bottle
'Coca Cola doesn't have that kind of bottle,'
(Text, *School Camping*, line 83, Chappell)
- (4) (你们当中/之中/中间)谁有孩子？
(nǐmen dāngzhōng/zhīzhōng/zhōngjiān) shéi yǒu háizi?
2PL among who have child
'Amongst you, who has children?'
(Elicited, Lisha He, pers. comm.)

(5) 再说了，我一点儿睡意都没有。丝毫睡意也没有。

zài shuō le wǒ yìdiǎner kùnyì dōu méi yǒu. sīháo kùnyì yě méi yǒu
again say PFV 1SG a:bit sleepiness all NEG have tiny sleepiness also NEG have

‘In addition, I wasn’t sleepy at all, I didn’t feel any sleepiness.’

(Text, *School Camp*, line 270, Chappell)

Locative frame

(6) 她在这儿，

tā zài zhèr
3SG be.at here

‘She’s here.’

(Text, *School Camping*, line 175, Chappell)

Locative preposition

(7) 可是她们在那儿嚷嚷，拿手电筒上男厕所。

kěshi tāmen zài nàr rāngrang, ná shǒudiàntǒng shàng nán cèsuǒ
but 3PL at there shout take flashlight go.to men’s.toilet

‘But they were shouting there and took the flashlight with them to go to the men’s toilet.’

(Text, *School Camping*, line 262, Chappell)

Copula

(8) 将来出来还是是个工人吧!

jiānglái chūlai hái shì ge gōngrén ba
future come.out still COP CLF worker PRT

‘So when you graduate, (you’ll probably) still be a worker.’

(Text, *Education*, line 300, Chappell)

(9) 投档分数线可能还是五百三。

tóudǎng fēnshùxiàn kěnéng shì wǔbǎisān
put.in mark.line may COP five.hundred.thirty

‘The cut-off point (for accepting an application to university) might be 530.’

(Text, *Education*, line 44, Chappell)

2. Jilin Northeastern Mandarin 吉林东北官话 (Jilin, China)

Existential frame

(10) 那条河上有贼多小船儿

nei⁵¹ t^hjau³⁵ x^ɿ³⁵ ʂɑŋ⁵¹ jou²¹⁴ tsei³⁵ twɔ⁵⁵ ɕjau²¹⁴ tɕ^hwa³⁵

that CLF river upside there.be very a.lot little boat

‘There are a lot of little boats in that river.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

(11) 他们家院儿里有棵贼好看的老银杏儿

t^ha⁵⁵-mən tɕja⁵⁵ ɥɛ⁵¹ li²¹⁴ **jou²¹⁴** k^hɣ⁵⁵ tsei³⁵ xau²¹⁴k^han⁵¹ tɣ lau²¹⁴ jin³⁵ɕiŋ⁵¹.
3SG-PL house courtyard inside there.be CLF very good.looking MOD old gingko.tree

‘There is a beautiful old gingko tree in their courtyard.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

Possessive frame

(12) 俺有三个姨，一个舅。

an²¹⁴ **jou²¹⁴** san³⁵ kɣ ji³⁵, ji³⁵ kɣ tɕjou⁵¹
1SG have three CLF aunt one CLF uncle

‘I have three aunties and one uncle.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

(13) 你们都谁有苹果手表？

ni²¹⁴-mən tou³⁵ sei³⁵ **jou²¹⁴** p^hiŋ³⁵kwə²¹⁴ ʂou²¹⁴pjau²¹⁴

2SG-PL all who have Apple watch

‘Amongst you, who has an Apple watch?’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

Locative frame: **kʷ**²¹⁴ ‘be at’ < **kʷ**⁵⁵ ‘put’

(14) 我/俺今儿**搁**学校。

wo²¹⁴/an²¹⁴ tɕiŋ⁵⁵ **kʷ**²¹⁴ ɕɥɛ³⁵ɕjau⁵¹.

1SG today be.at school

‘I’m at school today.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

(15) 筷子**搁**厨房碗柜里

k^hwai⁵¹-tsɿ **kʷ**²¹⁴ tɕ^hu³⁵fɑŋ³⁵ wan²¹⁴kwei⁵¹ li.

chopstick be.at kitchen cupboard inside

‘The chopsticks are in the cupboard in the kitchen.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

Locative preposition

(16) 她喜欢**搁**公园里打太极拳。

t^ha⁵⁵ ɕi²¹⁴xwan kʏ²¹⁴ kuŋ⁵⁵ɥen³⁵ li ta²¹⁴ t^hai⁵¹tɕi³⁵tɕhɥan³⁵
 3SG like at park inside practice Taijiquan

‘She likes to practice Taijiquan in the park.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

‘put’

(17) 把手机搁下!

pa²¹⁴ ʂou²⁴tɕi⁵⁵ kʏ⁵⁵-ɕia!

DOM phone put-down

‘Put down your phone!’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

Copula

(18) 我妈是党委书记，我爸是（个）老师。

wʏ²¹⁴ ma⁵⁵ ʂɿ⁵¹ taŋ²¹⁴wei²¹⁴ʂu⁵⁵tɕi wʏ²¹⁴ pa⁵¹ ʂɿ⁵¹ (kʏ) lau²¹⁴ʂɿ⁵⁵.

1SG mother COP party.secretary 1SG father COP (CLF) teacher

‘My mother is a party secretary and my father is a teacher.’

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

(19) 明儿就是除夕了。

mí³⁵ tǎju⁵¹ ʂ⁵¹ tʂ^hu³⁵çi⁵⁵ lɿ.
tomorrow then COP Chinese.New.Year's.Eve PFV

'Tomorrow is Chinese New Year's Eve.'

(Boyang Liu, pers. comm.)

3. Beijing Mandarin (Pekinese) 北京官话 (Beijing, China)

Existential frame

(20) 起脊房旁边儿还有一间一顺水儿的小厦子。

qǐjǐfáng pángbiān hái yǒu yì jiān yíshùshuǐ de xiǎo shàzi.
house.with.a.triangle.roof beside also there.be one CLF single.sloped.roof MOD small house

'There's also a small house with a single sloped roof beside the house with a triangle roof.'

(Chen 1985: 313)

Possessive frame

(21) 没有点儿营生儿，整天游游摸摸儿的，可憋得慌呢。

méi yǒu diǎr yíngshengr, zhěng tiān yóuyoumōmōr de, kě biē de huang ne.
NEG have few work whole day have.nothing.to.do DUR very depressed VCOMP very PRT

'If one doesn't have work and has nothing to do, one must feel depressed.'

(Chen 1985: 315)

(22) 看他能有多大尿!

kàn ta néng yǒu duóta niào!
see 3SG can have how.much urine

‘(Let’s) see how capable he can be!’

(Chen 1985: 315)

Note: 有尿 ‘(LIT: have urine)’ is metaphorically use to express ‘have abilities, have capacities’.

Locative frame

(23) 他跟乡下呢。

tā gēn xiāngxia ne.
3SG be.at country CONT

‘He’s in the country.’

(Chen 1985: 90)

Locative preposition

(24) 他们跟街上站着呢。

tā-men gēnjiē shang zhàn zhe ne.

3-PL at street upside stand DUR CONT

‘They’re standing in the street.’

(Chen 1985: 90)

‘follow’

(25) 你别跟着我啊!

nǐ bié gēn zhe wǒ a!

2SG NEG.IMP follow DUR 1SG PRT

‘Don’t follow me!’

(Ke Xu pers. comm.)

Copula

(26) 他寻思咱们是省油儿的呢。

tā xínsi zán-men shì shěng yóu de ne.

3SG think 1-PL.INCL COP save oil NMLZ PRT

‘He thought we were those easy to handle.’

(Chen 1985: 250)

4. Shangshui Central Plains Mandarin (Shangshui, Henan, China)

Existential frame

(27) 前面儿**有**个人，咱问问他。

tɕ^hian³¹ miaə⁰ **iou⁵⁵** kə⁰ zən³¹, zan³¹ uən⁵¹~uən⁰ t^ha⁰
front there.be CLF person 1PL ask~ask 3SG

‘There is a person in front of us and we can ask him about it.’

(Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

Possessive frame

(28) 她没有啥意见。

t^ha⁵⁵ miou³⁵ sa⁵¹ i⁵¹⁻³⁵tɕian⁵¹.
3SG NEG.have what objection

‘She doesn’t have any objections.’

(Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

Note: *miou³⁵* is a fused morpheme of the negator and the possessive verb *iou⁵⁵* in Shangshui.

Locative frame

(29) 他里饭店**搁**学校里里。

t^ha⁵⁵ li⁰ fan⁵¹tian⁵¹ **kə³⁵** ɕyo³¹ɕiao⁵¹ li⁵⁵ li
3SG MOD restaurant be.at school inside PRT

‘His restaurant is in a/the school.’

(Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

Locative preposition

(30) 我搁俺姥家上里学。

uo⁵⁵ kə³⁵ an⁵⁵ lao⁵⁵ tɕie⁰ saŋ⁵¹ li⁰ ɕyo³¹
1SG at 1PL grandmother home attend FOC school

‘It is in my grandmother’s hometown that I attended school.’

(Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

‘put’

(31) 桌子我才搁上去书。

tsuo³⁵tsɿ⁰ uo⁵⁵ ts^hai³¹ kə³⁵-saŋ⁰ su³⁵.
table 1SG just put-up book

‘As for the table, I just put some books on it a minute ago.’

(Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

Copula

(32) 那是我里书包。

na⁵¹ sɿ⁵¹ uo⁵⁵ li⁰ su⁵⁵ pao³⁵
 that COP 1SG MOD bag
 ‘That is my bag.’
 (Yujie Chen, *Field Notes*)

5. Jishou Southwestern Mandarin 吉首西南官话 (Jishou, Hunan, China)

Existential Frame

(33) 墙上有些网网儿网网儿的。
 dʒiaŋ¹¹ saŋ iəu⁴² çiei uaŋ⁴² uə̃ uaŋ⁴² uə̃ ti.
 wall upside there.be some web-RDP web-RDP PRT
 ‘On the wall there were some small web-like things.’
 (Q. Li 2002: 224)

Possessive frame

(34) 你这个牛有奶没?
 ɲi⁴¹ tsɿ³⁵ ko ɲiəu¹¹ iəu⁴² lai⁵⁵ mei?
 2SG this CLF cow have milk NEG
 ‘Does this cow of yours have milk?’
 (Q. Li 2002: 366)

Locative frame

(35) 佢都没**到**身边儿，着老的自家做啖。

ŋə¹¹ təu⁵⁵ mi³⁵ **tau³⁵** sən⁵⁵piə⁵⁵, ts'o³⁵ lau⁴²ti tsɿ³⁵ka tsəu³⁵ lai.
child all NEG be.at body.side need old.person self do PRT

'None of the children are with me so I have no choice but to do everything myself.'

(Q. Li 2002: 322)

(36) 他讲跟倒就走，若这半天还**到**屋里啖？

t'a⁵⁵ kaŋ⁴² kən⁵⁵tau tɕiəu³⁵ tsəu⁴², zo³⁵ tsɿ³⁵ pən³⁵t'ian⁵⁵ a¹¹ **tau³⁵** u¹¹li lai?
3SG say immediately then leave how.come this half.day still be.at home PRT

'He said that he was immediately leaving, so how come he's still at home after all this time ?'

(Q. Li 2002: 336)

Locative preposition

(37) 他**到**我屋里吃的饭。

t'a⁵⁵ **tau³⁵** ŋo⁴² u¹¹li tɕ'i¹¹ ti fan³⁵.
3SG at 1SG home eat FOC meal

'It is at my place that he had a meal.'

(Q. Li 2002: 342)

‘arrive, go’

(38) 你到过北京没?

ni⁴² tau³⁵ ko pei¹¹tɕin⁵⁵ mi?

2SG arrive EXP Beijing NEG

‘Have you ever been to Beijing?’

(Q. Li 2002: 340)

Copula

(39) 我是老三。

ŋo⁴² sɿ³⁵ lau⁴²san⁵⁵.

1sg COP Laosan_{NICKNAME}

‘I’m Laosan.’

(Q. Li 2002: 336)

Jin Branch

6. Jinyuan Jin 晋源 (Jinyuan, Shanxi, China)

Existential frame

- (40) ... 有一个县官
 iɿu⁴² iəʔ² kuai³⁵ ɕiæ³⁵ kuaŋ¹¹
 there.be one CLF county official
 ‘(Once long ago,) there was a county official,’
 (Wang Wenqing 2007: 257)

Possessive frame

- (41) 保不住他有做的嘞。
 pau⁴²-pəʔ²-tsɿu³⁵ t'a¹¹ iɿu³⁵ tsuəʔ²⁻²¹ təʔ² ləʔ²
 maybe 3SG have do NOM PRT
 ‘It could be that he is busy (lit: He probably has something to do).’
 (Wang 2007: 246)

Locative frame

- (42) 那告说不在这勒。
 na¹¹ kau³⁵ fəʔ² pəʔ² tsai³⁵ tsəʔ²⁻²¹ləʔ² .
 DEM tell say NEG be.at here
 ‘People say that it’s not here.’
 (Wang 2007: 250)

Locative preposition

(43) 他在树底下头看书呢。

t'a¹¹ **tsai**³⁵ fu³⁵-æ¹¹ ti⁴²-tʃu¹¹ k'aŋ³⁵-fu¹¹ ləʔ²
3SG at tree-DIMN under read-book PRT

'He is reading a book under the tree.'

(Wang Wenqing 2007: 250)

Copula

(44) 我是老王。

ɣʃ⁴² sɿ³⁵ lau⁴²ɔ¹¹
1SG COP Laowang_{NICKNAME}

'I'm Laowang.'

(Wang Wenqing 2007: 246)

7. Xinzhou Jin 忻州

Existential frame & possessive frame

(45) 有个老汉有三个儿子。

iəu³¹³ kuæ lɔ³¹³⁻⁴²xã⁵³ **iəu**³¹³ sɔ̃³¹³⁻⁴² kuæ³¹ ər³¹

there.be CLF old.man have three CLF son

‘There was an old man who had three sons.’

(Hou and Wen 1993: 316)

Possessive frame

(46) 以为老汉真的有咯钱。

i³¹³⁻²⁴vei³¹ lɔ³¹³⁻⁴²xã⁵³ tɕəŋ²¹³tiə iəu³¹³⁻⁴²-lɔ tɕiẽ³¹

think old.man really have-PFV money

‘(They) mistakenly thought that the old man really had got rich (LIT. got money).’

(Hou and Wen 1993: 317)

Locative frame

(47) 爪嘞怎么这半天啦还在家儿嘞?

tsua³¹³liə tɕl⁵³ puõ⁵³t⁵³iẽ³¹³⁻³¹ la xã³¹ tsæ⁵³ tɕiõr³¹³ liə?

how this half.day PFV still be.at home PRT

‘How come she’s still at home after all this time?’

(Hou and Wen 1993: 291)

Locative preposition

- (48) 第三天在三儿家吃
 ti⁵³ sã³¹³⁻³³ t'iɛ³¹³⁻³³ tsæ⁵³ sã³¹³ əɾ³¹ tɕiɛɾ³¹³ tɕ'əŋ².
 ORDthree day at three son family eat
 'On the third day, (he) ate at his third son's home.'
 (Hou and Wen 1993: 317)

Copula

- (49) 我是三小子。
 ŋɛ³¹³ sɿ⁵³ sã³¹³ çiaŋ².tə.
 1SG COP three little.NMLZ
 'I'm the third eldest.'
 (Hou and Wen 1993: 289)

8. Changsha Xiang 长沙湘语 (Changsha, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

- (50) 那公社边上咧，就有一家小小的供销社。
 la²⁴ kən³³sɿ⁴⁵ piẽ³³san²¹ liɛ⁴¹, tɕiəu²¹ iəu⁴¹ i²⁴ tɕia³³ çiau⁴¹çiau⁴¹ti kən³³çiau³³sɿ⁴⁵
 that commune beside MOD then there.be one CLF small SP shop
 'There is a small shop beside the commune.'

(Wu 2005: 300 d)

Possessive frame

(51) 我还有好多事冒做完。

ŋo⁴¹ xai¹³ iəu⁴¹ xau⁴¹to³³ si²¹ mau²¹ tsəu⁴⁵-yē¹³.

1SG still have many thing NEG.PFV do-finish

‘I still have a lot of things to do.’

(Wu 2005: 357)

Locative verb

(52) 我哥哥不在家。

ŋo⁴¹ ko³³ko mau²¹ tsai²¹ u²⁴li.

1SG E.brother NEG be.at home

‘My elder brother is not at home.’

(Wu 2000: 336)

*ku*¹³*ty*²⁴~*ku*¹³*ta*²¹ ‘be at’ [+animate] (< ‘squat at, squat to’)

(53) 猫^{咕哒}窝里。

mau³³ **ku¹³ta²¹** o³³ li⁴¹.

cat be.at nest inside

‘The cat is in its bed.’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm)

(54) 你爸爸**咕哒**屋里有?

ŋi⁴¹ pa¹³ pa ku¹³ ta²¹ u²⁴ li⁴¹ mau¹¹?

2SG father be.at home NEG

‘Is your father at home?’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm)

Locative preposition with *ku¹³* as ‘stay’ in (56)

(55) 我还**古哒**那只猪栏中间哆生咖一盆炭火。

ŋo⁴¹ xai¹³ **ku¹³ ta²¹** la⁴⁵ tsa²⁴ tɕy³³ lan¹³ tsən³³⁴ kan³³ to³³ sən³³-ka⁴¹ i²⁴ pən¹³ t^han⁴⁵ xo⁴¹

1SG then **at** that CLF pigsty middle MOD light-ASP one CLF charcoal.fire

‘I then lit a charcoal fire in the middle of the pigsty.’

(Wu 2005: 243)

(56) 它就干脆**古在**屋里等现成的。

t^ha³³ tɕiəu²¹ kan³³ ts^hei⁴⁵ **ku¹³ tsai²¹** u²⁴-li tən⁴¹ ɕiɛ̃²¹ tsən¹³ ti⁴¹.

it then at.the.end stay at home wait.for ready-made SFP

'In the end, it (the dog) stayed home and waited to be fed.'

(Wu 2005: 244)

'squat'

(57) 他跼得地上屙屎。

t^ha³³ ku¹³ tɿ²⁴ ti⁵⁵ san¹¹ o³³sɿ⁴¹.

3SG squat at floor upside poop

'He squatted on the floor pooping.'

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm.)

Copula

(58) 咯个是书尼个是笔。

ko³¹³ kɿ³³ st⁴² ɕy³¹, n³³ kɿ³³ st⁴² pi²⁴.

this CLF COP book that CLF COP pen

'This is a book, that is a pen.'

(Wu 2005: 117)

9. Longhui Xiang (Longhui, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(59) 那山上有老虫啊，千万莫去啊。

n³¹ sā⁵⁵ zǎ³¹ ɰ³¹ ne³¹ dzəŋ⁵⁵ a³⁵, tsɿ⁵⁵ vā⁵⁵ mo³⁵ tɕ'i²⁴ a³⁵.
that mountain upside there.be tiger PRT absolutely NEG go PRT

'There are tigers on that mountain. You absolutely must not go there.'

(Ding and Luo 2006: 20)

Possessive frame

(60) 其喊你去，总有么个事着。

tɕi³¹ xā³¹ n³¹ tɕ'i²⁴, tsəŋ³¹ ɰ³¹ mo³¹ ke⁵⁵ zɿ²⁴ tɕa⁵⁵.
3SG tell 2SG go certain have some CLF matter PRT

'He told you to go, so there must be something.'

(Ding and Luo 2006: 12)

(61) 我今日有几个同学要来哈。

ŋo³¹ tɕe⁵⁵ ŋ³¹ ɰ³¹ tɕi³¹ ke³¹ dəŋ¹³ ɕu⁵⁵ ie³⁵ ne³¹ xa⁵⁵.
1SG today have several CLF classmate intend come PRT

'Today I have several classmates who are coming over.'

(Ding and Luo 2006: 24)

Locative frame

(62) 就你在咯里，给我安起天线着。

ɖʌ²⁴ ɳ³¹ ze³¹ ko³¹ni³¹, ke⁵⁵ ŋo³¹ ǎ⁵⁵-tɕi³¹ tĩ⁵⁵si⁵⁵ tɕe⁵⁵.
while 2SG be.at here for 1SG install-INC antenna PRT

‘Now that you are here, you could install the antenna for me.’

(Ding 2009: 219)

Locative preposition ‘at’

(63) 其晒起在床上。

tɕi³¹ k‘uẽ²⁴-tɕi³¹ ze³¹ zã¹³ zĩã³¹.
3SG sleep-DUT at bed upside

‘He’s sleeping in the bed.’

(Ding 2009: 218)

Copula

(64) 你也 是 党员着，敢讲咯样格话？

ŋ²¹ ia²¹ zɿ²¹ kəu⁴⁴ tã²¹yẽ²¹ tɕia⁴⁴, kã²¹ kã²¹ ko²¹ oã⁴⁴ ke²¹ ua⁴⁴
2SG also COP CLF party.member PRT dare talk this kind MOD speech

‘Aren’t you also a party member, yet you dare to talk like this?’

(Ding 1996: 363)

10. Loudi Xiang 娄底湘语 (Loudi, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(65) 他喊还有绿豆子啊，粟米啊，滴个家伙。

tʰo³ xã² a¹³ io² lɿu³⁵tʰiɿ¹tsɿ² a³, siø¹³mĩ² a³, ti⁵ kɿ² tɔ³xø².

3SG say also there.be mung.bean PRT millet PRT some CLF thing

‘He said that there are also mung beans, (foxtail) millet and some other things.’

(Peng 2006: 389)

Possessive frame

(66) 尔有几个老兄?

ŋ⁴² io⁴² tɕi⁴²kɿ⁵ lɿ⁴²ɕioŋ³?

2SG have how.many CLF E.brother

‘How many elder brothers do you have?’

(Peng 2000: 357)

Locative frame

(67) 印俺老兄冇在屋里。

ŋ⁴²nā̄ lɿ⁴²ɕioŋ mɿ¹¹ ts'e u³⁵li.
1PL E.brother NEG be.at home

'My elder brother is not at home.'

(Peng 2000: 356)

(68) 尔架界在哪里啊? 在屋里啊?

ŋ⁴² tɔ³⁵ka⁵ t'e¹ la⁴²li³ a²¹? t'e¹ u³⁵li³ a³³¹?
2SG just.now be.at where prt ? be.at home PRT

'Where were you just now? At home?'

(Peng 2006: 129)

Locative preposition

(69) 他在城里做路。

t'o⁴⁴ t'e¹ t'ɿn¹³ tsɿ¹li⁵ tsɿu³⁵lɿu¹¹.
3SG at town inside do.business

'He works in town.'

(Peng 1998: 303)

Copula

(70) 他是哪个个崽哪?

tʰo⁴⁴ tsʰɿ¹ la⁴²kɔ⁵ kɿ³ tse⁴² la⁵?

3SG COP which.one CLF son Q

‘Whose son is he?’

(Peng 2006: 387)

11. Rucheng patois (Rucheng, Hunan, China)

Existential ‘there be’

(71) 山頂頭有個棚子。

sa³³-tjɿ²¹-təu⁵⁵ jou³³ kɿ³⁴ poŋ⁵⁵tɕi³³.

mountain-summit-head have CLF cabin

‘There’s a cabin on the top of the mountain.’

(Lisha He pers. comm.)

Possessive

(72) 渠有四個細俵子。

tɕi³³ jou³³ sɿ³⁴ kɿ³⁴ sei^{55/34}lai²¹tɕi⁴³.

3SG have four CLF child

‘She has four children.’

(Lisha He pers. comm.)

Locative frame

(73) □老伯在辦公室。

ŋau²¹ lau²¹pɔ³⁴ ts^hai⁴³ pa⁴³koŋ³³sæ²¹.

1SG.POSS.KIN elder.brother be.at office

‘My brother is in the office.’

(Lisha He pers. comm.)

Locative preposition

(74) 渠愛在屋□做事。

tçi³³ wai³⁴ ts^hai⁴³ wu³⁴naŋ⁴³ tsu³⁴ʂ⁴³.

3SG like at home-LOC work

‘She likes to work at home.’

(Lisha He pers. comm.)

Copula

(75) 渠系（個）老師，渠系（個）學生。

tɕi³³ **hei⁴³** (kɛi³⁴) lau²¹ɕ³³, tɕi³³ **hei⁴³** (kɛi³⁴) xu⁴³sən³³.
 3SG COP (CLF) teacher 3SG COP (CLF) student
 ‘She is a teacher and he is a student.’
 (Lisha He pers. comm.)

12. Yichun Gan (Yichun, Jiangxi, China)

Existential frame ‘there be’ iu⁴² 有

(76) 箇里有只鸟立。

ko³⁴li iu⁴² tɕia? tieu⁴²⁻³³li.
 DEM-LOC there.be CLF bird
 ‘Here is a bird.’
 (Li 2018: 63)

Possessive frame

(77) 我俚只姐夫**有**只伢俚仔，初中都有毕业...

ŋo³⁴li tɕia? tsia⁴²fu **iu⁴²** tɕia? ŋa⁴⁴li-tsi?, ts^hɿ³⁴tɕioŋ³⁴ tu³⁴ mau³⁴ pi?ŋiɛ?
 1PL CLF brother-in-law have CLF boy-DIM middle.school FOC NEG.have graduate
 ‘My brother-in-law has a son, (he) did not finish middle school.’
 (Li 2018: 166)

Locative frame

(78) 渠屋里就在箇近边立儿。

kie³⁴ uʔli tɕ^hiu²¹³ ts^hœ²¹³ ko³⁴ tɕ^hin²¹pien³⁴li.

3SG home FOC be.at this near.side

‘His house is right nearby.’

(Li 2018: 123)

Locative preposition

(79) 渠坐在我（格）前头。

kie³⁴ ts^ho²¹ ts^hœ²¹³ ŋo³⁴ (ko) tɕ^hien⁴⁴t^hœu.

3SG sit LOC 1SG MOD front

‘He sat in front of me.’

(Li 2018: 56)

Copula

(80) 我(是)宜春人。

ŋo³⁴ (ɕi²¹³) ni⁴⁴tɕ^hyn³⁴ nin⁴⁴.

1SG COP Yichun person

‘I am a local in Yichun.’

(Li 2018: 231)

13. Nanchang Gan (Nanchang, Jiangxi, China)

Existential frame

(81) 熱天裏還往往有洪水

let⁷t^hien¹ li hai² wong³wong³ **yi**u³ fung⁵suii³,

summer inside in.addition often there.be flood

‘In the summer, on top of it, there often are floods.’

(Nanchang Weather, Sagart 1999)

Possessive ‘have’

(82) 箇個有文化有修養乃人

ko³ ko **yi**u³ win⁵fa **yi**u³ xiu¹yong³ kë nyin⁵

this CLF have culture have education REL person

‘This person was very cultured and erudite.’

(Turnips, Sagart 1999)

Locative frame

- (83) 渠冇在屋裏
 cie³ mao⁶ ts^hai⁶ wuq⁷li,
 3SG NEG be.at house
 ‘He is not at home ...’
 (Sagart 1999)

Locative preposition

- (84) 在房間裏啊
 ts^hai⁶ fong⁵kan¹ li a,
 at apartment inside A_{TOP}
 ‘in the apartment’

Copula verb ‘be’

- (85) 你人是好有學問乃人啊
 n³len si⁶= hao³ yiu³= ^hoq⁷win⁶ kə[ko] nyin⁵ a,
 2SG COP very have knowledge REL person A
 ‘You are a very erudite person.’
 (Sagart 1999)

14. Anren Gan 安仁赣语 (Anren, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(86) 圈箕在里头**有**一只大蛇,

luã³⁵tʃi.ts'æ³¹ ti³¹tə **iu³¹** i³¹³ tʃa t'æ³¹ ʃa³⁵

Luanjizai inside have one CLF big snake

'There was a big snake inside Luanjizai Hill.'

(Chen 1995 : 239)

Possessive frame

(87) 你**有**嘛咯法子呢?

n̩³¹ **iu³¹** ma.ke fa³¹³tsɿ e?

2SG have what method PRT

'What method do you have?'

(Chen 1995: 244)

Locative frame

(88) 固只蛇还**在**圈箕在里头,

ku³¹ tʃa ʃa³⁵ ha³⁵ **ts'e³¹** luã³⁵tʃi.ts'æ³¹ ti³¹tə

this CLF snake still be.at Luanjizai inside

‘This snake still lives inside Luanjizai Hill.’

(Chen 1995: 240)

Copula

(89) 佢晓得固只崽日后啲**是**只败子啲。

tʃi³¹³ ʃɔ³¹³te ku³¹ tʃa tse⁵¹ i³¹³hə³¹tsi **sɿ³¹** tʃa p'æ³¹tsɿ ta.
3SG know this CLF son future COP CLF black.sheep PRT

‘He knows that this son will be a black sheep in the future.’

(Chen 1995: 241)

15. Pingjiang Gan 平江赣语 (Pingjiang, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(90) 院子里**有**两棵树。

yan⁵⁵tsɿ³⁵ li⁴² **iəu²¹** lion²¹ tɔu³³ ɕy²².
yard inside there.be two CLF tree

‘There are two trees in the courtyard.’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm.)

Possessive frame

(91) 他**有**两个哥哥。

t^ha³³ iəu²¹ liŋ²¹ ko⁵⁵ ko³³ko³³.

3SG have two CLF elder.brother

‘He has two elder brothers.’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm.)

Locative frame

(92) 锁匙**落**抽屉里。

sø³⁵çi³³ lo⁴² tɕ^həu³³t^hi⁵⁵ li⁴²

key be.at drawer inside

‘The key is in the drawer.’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm.)

Locative preposition

(93) 尔落别个□□受□气就跑到我□来。

ŋ²¹ lo⁴²p^hiɛ⁴²ko⁵⁵ ko³⁵ti⁴² ɕəu²² ta⁴²tɕ^hi⁵⁵ tɕ^hiəu²² p^hau³⁵ tau⁵⁵ ŋo²¹ i³⁵ lai¹³.

2SG at other there suffer PFV anger then run to 1SG here come

‘You suffered at the hands of others and then you came to me.’

(Lü and Peng 2020: 190)

‘fall’

(94) 太阳落□山。

t^hai⁵⁵iɔŋ¹³ lo⁴² ta⁴² san³³.

sun fall PFV hill

‘The sun is going down behind the hill.’

(Lü and Peng 2020: 189)

Copula

(95) 我里爷是医生。

ŋo²¹ li⁴² ia¹³ ʂ²¹ i³³si²².

1SG POSS.KIN father COP doctor

‘My father is a doctor.’

(Daxingwang Peng pers. comm.)

16. Shanghainese WU 上海吴语 (Shanghai, China)

Existential frame

(96) 房间里有只床。

Vongkae-lii xieu tsaq zong.

room-in there.be clf bed

‘There is a bed in the room.’

(Zhu 2006: 161)

Possessive frame

(97) 爸爸有交关谜谜子。

Papa **xieu** jiaokuae memetsir.

dad have many riddles

‘Dad had lots of riddles in his mind.’

(Zhu 2006: 183)

Locative verb

(98) 其辣辣屋里。

Xii **laqlaq** uqlii.

he be.at home

‘He is at home.’

(Zhu 2006: 110)

Locative preposition

(99) 其辣辣屋里睡觉。

Xii **laqlaq** uqlii khunkao.

s/he at home sleep

‘S/he’s sleeping at home.’

(Zhu 2006: 117)

Copula

(100) 其是江西人。

Xii **zir** Kongsjiinjin.

he COP Jiangxi-person

‘He’s from Jiangxi.’

(Zhu 2006: 157)

17. Ningbo Wu (Tianluo variety) 宁波话田螺方言

Existential ‘there be’

(101) 啥地方有旗袍卖啦？ 嚯。

so?⁵ di²²fɿ⁴⁴ **fy**²² dʒi²²bɔ²¹ ma²⁴ la²²?

what place there.be Qipao sell Q

‘Where (can we) buy Qipaos?’

(Ruan 2009: 246)

Note: *Qipao* refers to a kind of Chinese style dresses which are close-fitting

Possessive frame

(102) 诺好甯借个和，我自家有个和。

noʔ² hɔ⁴⁴ vən²¹ tɕia⁴⁴ fiɔʔ²fiəu²², ŋo²⁴ ʒi²²kuo⁴⁴ fiy²² fiɔʔ²fiəu²².
2SG good need.not borrow PRT 1SG self have PRT

‘You’d better not to borrow (it). I have one myself.’

(Ruan 2009: 170)

Locative verb

(103) 渠来的。

dʒi²⁴ lie²² ti⁵.
3SG be.at here

‘He’s here.’

(Ruan 2009: 34)

Locative preposition

(104) 弟弟来北京大学读书。

di²²di²² lie²² poŋ⁵tɕin⁵³da²²fiŋ² doŋ²ʂɿ⁵³.

younger.brother at Peking University study

‘My younger brother studies at Peking University.’

(Ruan 2009: 24)

‘come’

(105) 阿拉屋落多来走走。

eŋ⁵le² uoŋ⁵loŋ² təu⁵³ lie²² tso⁵³~tsø⁵³.

1PL home muc come walk~walk

‘Come and pay more visits to us.’

(Ruan 2009: 75)

Copula

(106) 我勿是木大, 我也晓得啥人 得我好.

ŋo²² vəŋ² zɿ²¹ moŋ²dəu²¹, ŋo²² fia²² ɕio⁵³təŋ⁵ soŋ⁵ŋin²² təŋ⁵ŋo²⁴ ho³⁵.

1SG NEG COP idiot 1SG also know who to 1SG good

‘I’m not an idiot and know who treats me well.’

(Ruan 2009: 125)

18. Tiantai Wu 天台吴语 (Tiantai, Zhejiang, China)

Existential frame

(107) 镬勒有粥

fɯɔʔ²³.ləʔ **fɪɻu**²¹⁴ tɕyɯʔ⁵
pot-in there.be porridge
'There's porridge in the pot.'

(Dai 2006: 136)

Possessive frame

(108) 我勑伞, 有雨衣。

fɯ²¹⁴ fiau⁵⁵ sɛ³²⁵, **fɪɻu**²¹⁴ fɪy²¹⁴⁻²¹i³³.
1SG not.want umbrella have raincoat
'I don't need an umbrella. I have a raincoat.'

(Dai 2006: 123)

(109) 佢拉个新书有啊弗? 有

gei²²⁴laʔ kou ɕiŋ³³ ɕy³³ **fɪɻu**²¹⁴ aʔ fəʔ^{5?} mɻu³³⁴⁻³¹.
3PL this new book have CONJ NEG no
'Do they have any new books?' 'No.'

(Dai 2006: 104)

Locative frame

(110) 乃儿在 哪去呢? 在北京

na²¹⁴⁻³³ fin²²⁴ **zei**²¹⁴ no²¹⁴⁻³⁵ kei.a?

2SG son be.at where Q

‘Where is your son?’

lei²¹⁴ pøʔ⁵⁻¹kin³³.

be.at Beijing

‘(He’s) in Beijing’

(Dai 2006: 135)

Note: Dai (2006: 135-136) states that *lei*²¹⁴ is an allomorph of *zei*²¹⁴ and *lei*²¹⁴ is more colloquial. Dai also states that preposition *zei*²¹⁴ 在 ‘at’ has undergone a lenition in pronunciation to *l-* and the final has become glottalised in many Wu dialects producing –Vʔ, *lei*²¹⁴ > ləʔ³ in fast speech, equivalent to use of character 勒 lAʔ² in Shanghainese or 辣 laʔ²³ or ləʔ²³ in Suzhou.

(111) 北京在 北边, 广州在 南边。

pøʔ⁵⁻¹kin³³ **lei**²¹⁴ pøʔ⁵.piE, ku⁵³²⁵⁻³²tɕiɻu³³ **lei**²¹⁴ nE²²⁴.piE.

Beijing be.at north Guangzhou be.at south

‘Beijing is in the north and Guangzhou is in the south.

(Dai 2006: 135)

Copula

(112) 佢是乃姆

gei²²⁴ zɿ²¹⁴⁻²¹ na²¹⁴⁻³⁵ m̩⁵¹.

3SG COP 2SG mother

‘She is his mother.’

(Dai 2006 2006: 135)

19. Taiwanese Southern Min 台湾闽南 (Taiwan, China)

Existential frame

(113) 第二樓 有 健身房。

Tē-jī lâu ū kiān-sin-pâng.

ORD-two floor there.be gymnasium

‘The second floor has a gym.’

(Lin 2015: 226)

(114) 溪裏得攞有（菅芒）喔

khe¹ = lai⁵-te² long² u⁷ hit⁴⁴ <F ^koan¹-^bang⁵ F> oh,
 creek = inside all have that reed PRT

‘There were reeds in the creek, ...’ (Texts, *Jesse’s narrative* line 131, Chappell)

Possessive frame

(115) 洪小姐有兩個兄弟。

Âng sió-chiá ū n̄ng ê hiaⁿ-tī.
 Ang Ms. has two CLF brother

‘Ms. Ang has two brothers.’

(Lin 2015: 227)

Locative frame

(116) 阮囡仔佇學校。

Gún gín-á tī hāk-hāu.
 1PL.EXL child be.at school

‘Our child is at school.’

(Lin 2015: 234)

Locative preposition

(117) 恁佇辦公室食中晝頓。

In tī pān-kong-sek chia̍h tiong-tàu-tng.

3PL at office eat lunch

‘They have lunch in the office.’

(Lin 2015: 235)

Copula

(118) 伊是美國人。

I sī Bí-kok lâng.

3SG COP America.person

‘He is American.’

(Lin 2015: 223)

20. Hui’an Southern Min 惠安閩南語 (Hui’an, Fujian, China)

Existential frame

(119) 搭有插頭無

ta?⁷ u⁴ tsha?⁷⁻⁸-thau² bo⁰

here there.be insert-head SFP

‘Is there a plug here?’

(Chen 2020: 356)

Possessive frame

(120) 伊有錢抑無

i¹ u⁴ tsin² aŋ⁸⁻⁴ bo²

3SG have money or not.have

‘Does he have money?’

(Chen 2020: 352)

Locative frame

(121) 冊包佢即搭

tsheŋ⁷⁻⁸pau¹ tu⁴/ti⁴ tsit⁷⁻⁸taŋ⁷

book.bag be.at here

‘The schoolbag is here.’

Copula

(122) 汝是大學生嘅

lu³ si⁴ tua⁵⁻⁴oŋ⁸⁻⁴siŋ¹ m⁰

2SG COP university.student SFP

‘Are you a university student?’

(Chen 2020: 353)

21. Chaozhou Min – Jieyang variety 揭阳闽南语 (Jieyang, Guangdong, China)

Existential frame

(123) ka²¹³⁻⁵³sek² lai³⁵ u³⁵⁻²¹ naŋ⁵⁵
classroom inside have person

‘There are people in the classroom.’

(Xu 2007: 222)

Possessive ‘have’

(124) ua⁵³ u³⁵⁻²¹ tio⁵⁵⁻¹¹suã³³ tua¹¹ zi¹¹tiaŋ⁵³
1SG have Chaoshan big dictionary

‘I have got the Chaoshan dictionary.’

(Xu 2007: 222)

Locative frame

(125) i³³ to³⁵⁻²¹ lai³⁵
3SG be.at home

‘S/he is at home.’

(Xu 2007: 148)

Locative preposition

(126) i³³ k’ia³⁵⁻²¹ to³⁵⁻²¹ k’eŋ²iō⁵⁵

3SG live at Jieyang

‘S/he lives in Jieyang.’

(Xu 2007: 148)

Copula

(127) i³³ m³⁵⁻²¹ si³⁵ hak²seŋ³³

3SG NEG COP student

‘S/he isn’t a student.’

(Xu 2007: 212)

22. Hainan Wenchang Southern Min 文昌闽南语 (Wenchang, Hainan, China)

Existential ‘there be’

(128) 過前有三哥弟

Kue¹¹-tai²² (u⁴²) ta⁴⁴ ko⁴⁴-di⁴².

before there.be three brothers

‘There were three brothers before.’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

(129) 桌上**有**一支/把刀

Doh⁵ tsio⁴⁴ **u**⁴² dziak³ ki⁴⁴/be²¹ do⁴⁴.

table on there.be one CLF knife

‘There is a knife on the table.’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

Possessive frame

(130) 你**有**錢（冇）無

Du²¹ **u**⁴² tsi²² (du⁴²) bo²²?

2SG have money exist NEG

‘Do you have money?’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

Locative frame

(131) A⁴⁴-meng²² oi⁴² **du**⁴² o²¹-iau⁴².

A-Meng will be.at school

‘A-Meng will be at school.’

(Lee 2014: 828)

Locative preposition

(132) 無用把紙拾攔佇恭房裏

Bo²² dziong⁴² fue⁴² tua²¹ sioh⁵-kak³ dfu⁴² kong⁴⁴-bang²² lai⁴².
NEG use hold paper throw.away at toilet inside

‘Don’t throw paper in the bathroom.’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

‘live’

(133) 你只砍伊你也無用想佇

Du²¹ na⁴² ham²¹ i⁴⁴, du²¹ ia⁴⁴ bo²²-dziong⁴² tio⁴² dfu⁴².
2SG if hack 3SG 2SG also NEG-use want exist

‘If you hurt him, do not expect that you will live.’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

Copula verb ‘be’

(134) 我們是海南人

Gua²¹-mui²² ti⁴² fai²¹-nam²² nang²².

1PL COP Hainan people

‘We are Hainan people.’

(*Field Notes*, Hui-chi Lee)

23. Shaowu Northwestern Min 邵武闽语 (Shaowu, Fujian, China)

Existential ‘there be’

(135) 街上有顶口人。

kie²¹ ɕioŋ³⁵ iou⁵⁵ tin⁵⁵ vai⁵⁵ nin²².

street on there.be very many person

‘There are many people on the street.’

(Ngai 2021: 441)

Possessive frame

(136) 我又有个问题。

xan³⁵ iou³⁵⁻⁵⁵ iou⁵⁵ ɕi²² kai²¹³ uən²¹³tʰi²².

1SG again have one CLF question

‘I have another question.’

(Ngai 2021: 181)

Locative frame

(137) 有□处, 畏啥?

iɔu⁵⁵ xaŋ³⁵ t^hu⁵⁵⁻³⁵ ʋi²¹³ ɕia^{53?}

there.be 1SG be.at afraid.of what

‘When I am here, what can you possibly be afraid of?’

(Ngai 2021: 445)

Copula

(138) □多皆是邵武人。

xaŋ³⁵taɪ²¹ ka³⁵ ɕi⁵⁵ ɕiau²¹³u⁵⁵ nin²².

1PL.EXCL all COP Shaowu person

‘We are all Shaowu people.’

(Ngai 2021: 451)

24. Fuzhou Northeastern Min 福州闽语 (Fuzhou, Fujian, China)

Existential frame ‘there be’

(139) 马潭边有蜀兜白玉兰树。

ma³¹⁻¹¹t-luo²³²⁻⁴⁴p-βien⁴⁴ **ou-u**²⁴²⁻⁴⁴ soʔ⁵⁻⁴ t-lau⁴⁴ paʔ⁴⁴⁻¹¹ nyʔ⁵⁻⁴ laŋ⁵³ts'iu²¹³
 roadside there.be one CLF white magnolia
 'There is a white magnolia at the roadside.'
 (Zheng 1985: 309)

Possessive frame

(140) 伊**有**三诸娘团。
 i⁴⁴ **ou-u**²⁴²⁻⁴⁴ saŋ⁴⁴⁻⁵⁴ ts-ʒieʔ²³ tsy⁴⁴⁻⁵⁴nøyn⁵⁴⁻³¹k-ŋiaŋ³¹
 3SG have three CLF daughter
 'He has three daughters.' (Zheng 1985:312)

Locative frame *tuoʔ5* < 'adhere, hit the target' 着

(141) 老王**着**楼顶。
 lo³¹⁻²¹ uoŋ⁵³ **tuoʔ5 lau⁵³⁻³¹t-liŋ³¹.
 old Wang be.at upstairs
 'Old Wang is upstairs.'
 (Liang 1990: 127)**

Locative preposition

(142) 伊着门哩做记认。

i⁴⁴ tuo?⁵ muoŋ⁵³ le⁰ tso²¹³⁻²¹ ki²¹³⁻⁵³ neiŋ²⁴².

3SG at door-on do mark

‘He makes a mark on the door.’

(Liang 1990: 129)

‘hit the target’

(143) 拍三枪, 着两枪。

p‘aŋ¹³ saŋ⁴⁴ ts‘-zuoŋ⁴⁴, tuo?⁵ laŋ²⁴²⁻⁴⁴ ts‘-zuoŋ⁴⁴.

shoot three gun hit.the.target two gun

‘(He) shot three times and hit the target twice.’

(Liang 1990: 127)

Copula verb ‘be’

(144) □是公家其。(artic le on 其 & 过 by Liang Yuzhang) page 74

tsui⁵³ si²¹ kuŋ⁵⁵ka⁵⁵ ki⁵³

this COM state NMLZ

‘This is the state’s (property).’

(Chen 1998: 138)

25. Shangyou Hakka 上犹客家话 (Shangyou, Jiangxi, China)

Existential frame

(145) 屋场上有^有两兄弟。

vuʔ³ts^hɔŋ¹¹-sɔŋ⁵³ **iu²⁴** liɔŋ³¹ ɕiaŋ²⁴t^hi⁵³.
village-at there.be two brothers

‘In the village, there were two brothers.’

(Huang 2005: 842)

Possessive ‘have’

(146) 该当有^有油，有^有米，有^有柴，有^有草。

kai¹¹tɔŋ⁵³ **iu²⁴** iu¹¹ **iu²⁴** mi³¹, **iu²⁴** ts^hai¹¹ **iu²⁴** ts^hau³¹.
this.place have oil have rice have firewood have straw

‘This place has oil, rice, firewood and straw.’

(Huang 2005: 843)

(147) 个个有^有事，你还来浪歇。(No IPA provided by the authors)

GEGE **iu²⁴** SHI, NI HAI LAILANG XIE.
everyone have thing 2SG still PROG play

‘Everyone has something to do, but you’re still playing around’

(Lai & Duan 2012: 25)

Locative frame

(148) 昨晡日厝寻了你，你□在屋家。

ts^hoʔ³pu¹¹niʔ⁵ ɲai¹¹ tɕ^hin¹¹-le¹¹ ni¹¹, ni¹¹ nai¹¹ ts^hoi²⁴ vuʔ³k^hua²⁴.

yesterday 1SG earch-ASP 2SG 2SG NEG be.at home

‘Yesterday I looked for you, but you weren’t at home.’

(Huang 2005: 756)

Locative preposition

(149) 唔晓得牛嬷在路放牛崽哩。

ŋ¹¹ ɕiau³¹-ti²⁴ niu¹¹ma¹¹ ts^hoi²⁴ lu⁵³-sɔŋ⁵³ fɔŋ⁵³ niu¹¹tse³¹ le¹¹

NEG know ox.Fem at road-on give.birth calf PRT

‘(He) didn’t know that the cow had given birth to a calf on the road.’

(Huang 2005: 842)

Copula

(150) 阿哥是蛮懒尸。

a²⁴-ko²⁴ hi⁵³ maŋ¹¹ laŋ²⁴sɿ²⁴

E.brother be very lazy

‘The elder brother was a slob.’

(Huang 2005: 842)

26. Liancheng Hakka 连城客家话 (Liancheng, Fujian, China)

Existential frame

(151) 有一个学生喊道小青。

iau³³ i³⁵-kuə³ hau⁷⁵saŋ³³ ha³tau³ siu⁵¹ts‘eŋ³³

there.be one-CLF student be.named Xiaoqing

‘There was a student called Xiaoqing.’

(Xiang 1997: 357)

Possessive ‘have’

(152) 我有一个朋友会开飞机。

ŋuə⁵⁵ iau³³ i³⁵-kuə³ p‘aŋ⁵⁵iau⁵¹ fuə⁷⁵ k‘øə³³ fi³³ki³³.

1SG have one-CLF friend can open plane

‘I have a friend who can fly a plane.’

(Xiang 1997: 359)

Locative frame < te³⁵ 着 ‘adhere, wear’

(153) 我书包还**着**教室底。

ŋuə⁵⁵ ɣuə³³puə³³ va⁵⁵ **te**³⁵ kuə³³ɣlə³⁵-tai⁵¹

1SG backpack still be.at classroom-in

‘My backpack is still in the classroom.’

(Xiang 1997: 247)

Locative preposition

(154) 佢**着**教室底看书。

trɥə⁵⁵ **te**³⁵ kuə³³ɣlə³⁵-tai⁵¹ ŋia³⁻¹¹ ɣuə³³.

3SG at classroom-in read book

‘She’s reading in the classroom.’

(Xiang 1997: 247)

Copula verb ‘be’

(155) 佢割个都**系**大个。

trɥə⁵⁵ kə³⁵ kuə³ tie³³ **hai**⁵⁵ t‘uə¹¹ kuə³.

3SG cut NMLZ all COP big NMLZ

‘What he scythed (rice) were all large ones.’

(Xiang 1997: 90)

27. Nanning Pinghua 南宁平话 (Nanning, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame: *jěu* 有 [jəu¹³]

(156) 佢讲佢队学校有好多女仔，介绍色只系你。

gěi gāang gěidòì hàakgáau **jěu** hāau dô něizāai, gáaillù llāk zēt hǎi něi.
3SG say 3PL school there.be very many girl introduce some CLF give you

‘S/he says there are many girls at their school, and s/he will introduce some to you.’

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

Possessive

(157) 我有水呀，沟个番！

ŋa¹³ **jəu¹³** tui³³ a³³, jən⁵³ kə⁵⁵ pɔ²⁵
1SG have water SFP cold MOD SFP

‘I have water, (but) it is cold!’

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

Locative frame

(158) 老子住那的?

lau¹³tʃi³³ tʃəi²² na³³tɪk⁵?

father be.at where

Where is (your) father?

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

佢住屋头。

kəi¹³ tʃəi²² uk³təu¹¹

3SG be.at home

'He is at home.'

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

Locative preposition: zèi [tʃei²²]

(159) 我住香港看见佢(个)□。

ngāa zèi yānggāng hǎngín gēi (gé) ām

1SG at HongKong see 3SG MOD mother

'I saw his/her mother in Hong Kong.'

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

'live' zèi [tʃei²²]

(160) 细的个间房我住,

llái-dík gé gâan fung ngãa zèi
small-NMLZ DEM CLF room 1SG live

'I'll stay in the small room, ...'

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

(161) [住]个地方呢, 就住[煮饭]个地方。

[zèi] gé dèifûng née zèu zèi [zēi faan] gé dèifûng
live MOD place FP then at cook rice MOD place

'The place where (she) lives, is the place where she/one does the cooking (i.e. kitchen),'

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

Copula: lli 是 [ʃi²²]

(162) 你队是广东人, 我队是广西人, 佢队都是南方人。

něidòì lli gūngdûng yan, ngãadòì lli gūngllâi yan, wandòì dū lli naam-fûng yan.
2PL COP Guangdong person 1EXCL COP Guangxi person 1INCL all COP south-side person

'You are Guangdong people, we are Guangxi people, and we are all Southerners.'

(*Field Notes*, Hilário de Sousa)

28. Hezhou Jiudu Pinghua 贺州九都平话 (Hezhou Jiudu, Guangxi, China)

Existential frame

(163) 老时有一个倪老者人,

ləu²²si²¹³ xau²² iə²² ɲi⁴³⁵ ləu²²tsie⁵⁵ ɲi²¹³
long.ago there.be one CLF elderly person

‘Long ago, there was an elderly man.’

(Zhang 2005: 289)

Possessive frame

(164) 你有几倪女?

ɲiə⁵⁵ xau²² ki⁴³⁵ ɲi⁴³⁵ ɲy²²?
2SG have how.many CLF daughter

‘How many daughters do you have?’

(Zhang 2005: 291)

Locative frame

(165) 盐油柴米在哪里?

iə²¹³ y²¹³ tsiə²¹³ mai²² tsai²² na³³ly²²?

salt oil kindling rice be.at where

‘Where are the salt, oil, kindling and rice?’

(Zhang 2005: 299)

Locative preposition

(166) 一座宫殿出现在眼前。

iə²² tsuə³³ kiəŋ⁴³⁵ tie³³ sui²² iə³³ tsai²² ŋai²² tsie²¹³

one CLF palace appear at eye front

‘A palace appeared before her eyes.’

(Zhang 2005: 294)

Copula

(167) 哪倪是大姊。

na²² ŋi⁴³⁵ yə³³ ta³³ tsəi⁵⁵

which CLF COP big sister

‘Which one was the elder sister, ...’

(Zhang 2005: 290)

29. Xinyi Yue 信宜粤语 (Xinyi, Guangdong, China)

Existential frame

(168) 罍煲□有饭么?

ɛŋ⁵³ pou⁵³-ɛŋ³⁵ **jeu**²³ fan¹¹ mɔ³³?

pot-in there.be riceprt

'Is there any rice in the pot?'

(Luo 1987: 222)

Possessive frame

(169) k'øi²³ kəm⁵³ nin²³ **jeu**²³ kei³⁵ tɔ⁵³ ʔui³³ tɛ¹¹ɔ³³?

3SG this.year have how many year PRT

'How old is he this year?'

(Luo 1987: 222)

Locative frame

(170) 你讲畀佢听，冇到己，亦有到□。

nei²³ kɔŋ³⁵ pei³⁵ k'øi²³ tei⁵³, mau²³ tou³³ kei³⁵, jek²² mau²³ tou³³ nøi³⁵.

2SG say DAT 3SG hear NEG be.at here also NEG be.at there

'You tell him that it's not here and it's also not there.'

(Luo 1987: 221)

Locative preposition

(171) 一只挂到面前，一只挂到背底。

jet⁵⁵ tsek⁵⁵ kua³³ tou³³ min¹¹ɦin⁵³, jet⁵⁵ tsek⁵⁵ kua³³ tou³³ pui³³tei³⁵.
one CLF hang at front one CLF hang at behind

‘(signs) One will hang at the front, and one behind.’

(Luo 1987: 232)

‘arrive’

(172) 先到为君，后到为臣。

ɦin⁵³ tou³³ wei⁴¹ kuen⁵³, heu¹¹ tou³³ wei¹¹ sen²³.
first arrive become king late arrive become vassal

‘LIT: The one who arrives first becomes a king, while the one who arrives late becomes a vassal.’

(Luo 1987: 194)

Copula

(173) 乜人？我系亚王。

met⁵⁵ ɦen²³? ɲɔ²³ hei¹¹ a³³wɔŋ²³.
who 1SG COP A-Wang

‘Who is it?’ ‘I’m A-Wang.’

(Luo 1987: 220)

30. Cantonese Yue 廣東粵語 Matthews & Yip (1994), Chappell texts

Existential frame

(174) daahnhaih yáuh yāt-go tiühgihn lē, ...
but there.be one-CLF condition PRT.TOP

‘But there was one condition on this, ...’

(Balcony Rendezvous text, Hilary Chappell)

Possessive frame

(175) ngóh yíhgīng yáuh-jó sāmseuhngyàhn lā.
1SG already have-PFV heart-in-person PRT

‘I’ve already got a sweetheart.’

(Balcony Rendezvous text, Hilary Chappell)

Locative frame

(176) Kéuih yìhgā hái bāanfóng-do.
3SG now be.at classroom-inside

‘She’s in the classroom now.’

(Field notes, Hilary Chappell)

Copula

(177) Jūk Yīng-Tòih **haih** luíhjái làih gā ma =
Name COP girl PRT prt prt

‘Juk Ying-Toi was a girl, to be sure.’

(Balcony Rendezvous text, Hilary Chappell)

31. Jixi Hui (Shangzhuang) 绩溪上庄徽语 (Jixi, Anhui, China)

Existential frame

(178) 有个渔民那口打鱼。

iə⁵⁵ ko³²⁴⁻³⁵ ny³²miã³² me²¹⁻²²xa⁰ tã⁵⁵ny³²
there.be CLF fisherman PROG_{there} fishing

‘There is a fisherman who is fishing.’

(Field Notes, Jian Wang)

Possessive frame

(179) 我有那本书。

ɑ⁵⁵ iə⁵⁵ nã²²³ pã⁵⁵⁻⁵³ ɕy²¹
1SG have that CLF book
'I have that book.'
(*Field Notes*, Jian Wang)

Locative frame

(180) 我是家里。
ɑ⁵⁵ se⁵⁵ ko²¹⁻²² ni⁰.
1SG be.at home inside
'I'm at home.'

Copula

(181) 我是老师。
ɑ⁵⁵ se⁵⁵ nã⁵⁵⁻⁵³ sɿ²¹.
1SG COP teacher
'I'm a teacher.'
(*Field Notes*, Jian Wang)

Locative preposition

(182) 我看书是教室里。

ɑ⁵⁵ k^hã³²⁴⁻³⁵ ɕy²¹ se⁵⁵ tɕiə³²⁴⁻³⁵ seŋ³²-ni⁰.

1SG read book at classroom-inside

‘I read books in the classroom.’

33. Yixian Hui 黟县徽语 Hirata, Shoji (1998)

Existential frame

(183) 还不曾。大约还有嘿一下儿就讲好了。

vu:e⁴⁴ pauw³sei³²⁴. t^ha³³i:u³ vu:e⁴⁴ iau⁵³-xɤe³ iei³-xœ⁵³neə⁰ tʃauw³²⁴ koŋ⁵³-xɤe⁵³ loe⁰.

still NEG:yet probably still there.be-ASP one-VCL.NMLZ then talk-finish PRT

‘Not yet. There’s still quite a while before they finish talking.’

(Hirata 1998: 289)

Possessive frame

(184) □个物有嘿几多重?

nei³-ka⁰ mauw³¹ iauw⁵³-xɤe³ tʃei⁵³tau³¹ ts^haŋ²⁴?

this-CLF thing have-ASP how.much weight

‘How much does this weigh?’

(Hirata 1998: 292)

Locative frame

(185) 是那□, 不是□□。

sɿ⁵³ noe³noŋ⁰, pau³ sɿ⁵³ nei³noŋ⁰

be.at there, NEG be.at here

‘It’s there, not here.’

(Hirata 1998: 289)

Locative preposition

(186) 渠是黟县工作。

k^hau⁴⁴ sɿ⁵³ iei³¹y:e³ kəŋ³¹tʃau³.

3SG at Yixian work

‘He works in Yixian.’

(Hirata 1998: 304)

Copula

(187) □是渠个书, 那本是渠家哥个。

nei³ sɿ⁵³ k^hau⁴⁴ ka⁰ ʃu³¹, noe³ paŋ⁵² sɿ⁵³ k^hau⁴⁴ kɤe⁰ kau³¹ ka⁰.

this COP 3SG CLF book that CLF COP 3SG family E.brother CLF

‘This is his book, and that one is his elder brother’s.’

(Hirata 1998: 302)

33. Wenzhou Rui'an Wu 瑞安吴语 (Rui'an, Zhejiang, China)

Existential frame

(188) tɕyo²¹⁴ ie²² **jiau²¹⁴** e⁴³⁴ paŋ³⁵ səm⁵⁵.

table upside there.be one CLF book

'There is a book on the table.'

(*Field Notes*, Milena Lazzaretti)

Possessive frame

(189) ŋ²¹⁴ **jiau²¹⁴** səm⁵⁵.

1SG have book

'I have books.'

Locative frame

(190) ni²¹⁴ **zɿ²¹⁴** nia³⁵ a? ŋ²¹⁴ (nau²¹⁴) **zɿ²¹⁴** gau⁴³⁴.

2SG be.at where INT 1SG (NEG) be.at here

'Where are you? I am (not) here.'

(*Field notes*, Milena Lazzaretti)

Copula

- (191) ni²¹⁴ zɿ²¹⁴ fu³⁵ zɿ²¹⁴ gi³¹ gi⁵³ a⁰ku⁵⁵?
 2SG COP NEG COP 3SG POSS brother
 ‘Are you his brother?’
 (*Field notes*, Milena Lazzaretti)

35. Fuqing Min 福清闽语 (Fuqing, Fujian, Chinan)

Existential frame

- (192) 有蜀头犬团故门兜嘞。
 u⁴¹ syɔ⁵¹⁻⁵⁵ lau⁵⁵ ken³²⁻⁵⁵ ŋian³²⁻⁵⁵ ka?⁵ muɔŋ⁵⁵lau⁵¹ lɛ⁰.
 there.be one CLF dog.DIM be.at door.side PRT
 ‘There’s a little dog at the door.’
 (Lin & Sheng 2018: 688)

Possessive frame

- (193) 我妈妈有三者姊。
 ŋua³² m⁵⁵ma²¹ u⁴¹ saŋ⁵¹⁻⁵⁵ tsia³² tsi²¹.
 1SG mother have three CLF elder.sister
 ‘My mother has three elder sisters.’
 (Lin Shaofang pers. comm. 2018 Mars)

Locative frame

(194) 小王无**故**厝。

seu³²uɔŋ⁵⁵ mɔ⁵⁵ **kaʔ⁵** ts^hɔ²¹.

Xiaowang NEG be.at house

‘Xiaowang is not at home.’

(Lin and Sheng 2018: 688)

Locative preposition

(195) 伊**故**北京出生。

i⁵¹ **kaʔ⁵** pɛʔ²⁻⁵kiŋ⁵¹ ts^huʔ²seŋ⁵¹.

3SG at Beijing be.born

‘He was born in Beijing’

(Lin and Sheng 2018: 689)

‘stick’

(196) 锁匙**故**门嘞拔无得落来。

sɔ²¹sie⁵⁵⁻³⁵ **kaʔ⁵** muɔŋ⁵⁵lɛ⁰ pɛʔ⁵-mɔ⁵⁵⁻³⁵liʔ²⁻⁵-lɔ⁵¹li⁰.

key stick door.LOC pull-NEG.obtain-fall.come

‘The key is stuck into the door and can’t be pulled out.’

(Lin and Sheng 2018: 688)

Copula

(197) 阿斗伊爸^故刘备。

aʔ²⁻⁵tau³² i⁵¹⁻⁵⁵ pa⁴¹ kaʔ⁵ lau⁵⁵pi⁴¹.
NAME 3SG father COP NAME

‘Adou’s father was Liu Bei.’

(Lin and Sheng 2018: 689)

34. Xianghua 乡话 (Guzhang, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(198) ni³⁵ sai⁵⁵-ta va²⁵ ba⁴¹ liau²⁵ la.
2SG body-LOC there.be CLF insect PRT

‘There’s an insect on you.’

(*Field notes*, Hilary Chappell)

Possessive frame

(199) zɿ³³ i⁴¹tɕin³³ va²⁵ i¹³-kəu tsa²⁵ liau⁴¹
3SG already have one-CLF son CRS

‘She already has a son.’

(Field notes, Hilary Chappell)

Locative frame

- (200) zɿ¹³ ts^hɿ²⁵ tɕi⁴¹ = ta
3SG be.at home = LOC
'She's at home.'

(Field notes, Hilary Chappell)

Locative preposition

- (201) in⁵⁵ tɕin⁵⁵tɕi²⁵ tɕi⁴¹ta pa¹³ lau¹³toŋ²⁵li¹³ pi⁴¹tɕiau²⁵ k^hun²⁵lan¹³, mai²⁵-ta u²⁵ tɕiəu²⁵, tɕiəu²⁵,
due.to economics home NEG.have workforce relatively difficult finally 1SG then then

tɕiəu²⁵ ts^hɿ²⁵ tɕi⁴¹ta tsɿ³³, tsɿ³³ ka³³ poŋ³³niɛn¹³ o⁵⁵-ɿŋ⁵⁵.

then at home do do VCL half.year agricultural.labour

'For economic reasons, there wasn't enough labour force at home, and it was difficult ; so finally I then, then, then did half a year as a farm labourer at home.'

(Field notes, Hilary Chappell)

Copula

- (202) ni²⁵ ts^hɿ²⁵ sa⁵⁵fu⁵⁵ ba^{0?}
2SG COP teacher Q

'Are you a teacher?'

(*Field notes*, Hilary Chappell)

36. Dabu Hakka 大埔客家话 (Dabu, Guangdong, China)

Existential frame

(203) 屋下有人。

vuk¹ ha¹ zju¹ ɲin².
room downside there.be person

'There is someone at home.'

(He 1993:74)

Possessive frame

(204) 好在伯婆靠有主意。

ho³cai⁴ bak¹po² kau⁴ riu¹ zhu³ri⁴.
ho³¹ts'ai⁵¹ pak²¹p'o²⁴ k'au⁵¹ zju⁴⁴ tʂu³¹ʒi⁵¹.

luckily wife rather have ideas

'Luckily the wife of the Earth God had a lot of ideas.'

(He 1993: 132)

Locative frame

(205) 佢有屋下。

ki² **zju¹** vuk¹ha¹.

3SG be.at room-downside

‘He is at home.’

(He 1993: 74)

Copula

(206) 佢系中学生。

ki² **hei⁴** tɕuŋ¹hok²saŋ¹

3SG COP middle.school.student

‘He’s a middle school student.’

(He 1993: 10)

37. Haikou Southern Min, Hainan 海口闽南语 (Haikou, Hainan, China)

Existential frame

(207) 房裏有儂。

ʔbaŋ²¹ lai³³ **u³³/ʔdu³³** naŋ²¹.

house inside there.be person

‘There is someone in the house.’

(Chen 1996: 28)

Possessive frame

(208) 我有三管筆。

va²¹³ u³³/ʔdu³³ ta²⁴ kuaŋ²¹³ ʔbit⁵

1SG have three CLF pen

‘I have three pens.’

(Chen 1996: 28)

Locative frame

(209) 我今夜昏無有室。

va²¹³ kim²⁴ me²¹hui²⁴ vo²¹ u³³/ʔdu³³ siu³⁵.

1SG today evening NEG be.at house

‘I am not at home tonight.’

(Chen 1996: 22)

Locative preposition

(210) 鋪有外邊曝日

fu²⁴ u³³/ʔdu³³ hua²⁴min²⁴ fak³ zit³

lay at outside expose.(to the sun) sun
'lay (it) outside in the sun.'
(Chen 1996: 22)

Copula verb 'be'

(211) 我共伊是同学。

va²¹³ kaŋ²⁴ i²⁴ ti³³ hoŋ²¹hiək⁵⁵

1SG and 3SG COP classmate

'He and I are classmates.'

(Chen 1996: Preface 17)

38. Linxia 临夏话 (Linxia, Gansu, China)

Existential frame

(212) 桌子上两串钥匙有呢。

tʂu³¹tʂi⁴¹ aŋ³¹ liaŋ⁵⁵ tʂ^huan³¹ ʏɛ³¹ʂ⁴¹ ju⁵⁵ ni.

table upside two bunch key there.be PRT

'There're two bunches of keys on the table.'

(Hao Li pers. comm.)

Possessive frame

(213) 我姐姐两个娃有呢。

ŋə⁵⁵ tɕe⁵⁵tɕe⁰ lian⁵⁵ kə⁵⁵ va²⁴ ju⁵⁵ ni⁵⁵.
1SG E.sister two CLF child have PRT

‘My elder sisters have two children.’

(Hao Li pers. comm.)

Locative frame

(214) 我姐姐家里有呢。

ŋə⁵⁵ tɕe⁵⁵tɕe⁰ tɕia³¹ni⁰ ju⁵⁵ ni⁵⁵
1SG E.sister home be.at PRT

‘My elder sister is at home.’

(Hao Li pers. comm.)

Copula

(215) 我爸爸老师是呢。

ŋə⁵⁵ pa⁵⁵pa⁰ lao⁵⁵ʂ²⁴ ʂ⁵⁵ni⁰.
1SG father teacher COP PRT

‘My father is a teacher.’

(Hao Li pers. comm.)

TIBETO-BURMAN

39. Nisu (Bijie, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

- (216) sei³³ ndo³³ ŋa³³ tha²¹ tɕhie³³ dzo²¹.
tree on bird one CLF there.be
'There's a bird in the tree.'

(Zhai 2011:185)

Possessive frame

- (217) na³³li⁵⁵ hɿ⁵⁵: “ŋo²¹ m̩³³lu³³ dzo²¹.”
Nali_{NAME} say 1SG idea there.be
'Nali said: "I have an idea".'

(Zhai 2011: 289)

Locative frame

- (218) ŋo²¹ bu¹³ su³³ hiẽ²¹ t̩hu³³ dzo⁵⁵ lei³³.

1SG POSS book home in be.at PRT

‘My book is at home.’

(Zhai 2011:191)

Copula

(219) tʂaŋ⁵⁵miŋ²¹ yu⁵⁵ vu⁵⁵ xu³³ zo²¹ ŋu²¹.

NAME vegetable sell NMLZ CLF COP

‘Zhangming is a vegetable vendor.’

(Zhai 2011:187)

40. Nasu (Luqunan, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(220) dʒɛ³³-thɔ²¹ku⁵⁵ tʂhe⁵⁵ne⁵⁵ tha²¹dzə³³ dzɔ²¹.

bed-under shoe one.pair there.be

‘There’s a pair of shoes under the bed.’

(Pu 2014: 31)

Possessive frame

(221) yo³³khɔ³³ dzɔ²¹ no³³ yo³³khɔ³³ zə³³, yo³³khɔ³³ ma²¹ dzɔ²¹ tʂhe³³khɔ³³ zə³³.

strength have NMLZ strength use strength NEG have idea use
 ‘(For)those having strength, contribute your strength and if not, contribute your ideas.’
 (Pu 2016: 216)

Locative frame

(222) thi⁵⁵ a⁵⁵ηo³³ mo³³ lu²¹tche⁵⁵ce⁵⁵ re³³mi³³tse⁵⁵fu²¹-ku⁵⁵ dzɔ²¹.
 3SG child DEF Luquan government-LOC be.at
 ‘His child is in the government of Luquan.’
 (Pu 2014: 33)

Copula

(223) tha⁵⁵ mu³³ no³³ su⁵⁵tʂu³³ tha²¹ lə³³ ne³³.
 3SG E.brother TOP teacher one CLF COP
 ‘His elder brother is a teacher.’
 (Pu 2016: 159)

41. Nuosu (Liangshan, Sichuan, China)

Existential frame

(224) ap mu shu kut xyp xi hni jyx vit jjo.

this year wedding VCL.time there.be

‘This year there is a wedding.’

(Gerner 2013: 456)

Possessive frame

(225) cop wox ggu dut go kax ddi ma sse **jjo?**
2P.PL among LOC INT.who CL son have

‘Who among them has a son?’

(Gerner 2013: 166)

Locative frame

(226) ip nyip ma hxa jjip go mu jy ix go **jjo** ssi ap dda.
today rain become SENT.TOP male name home be.at so perhaps

‘Today it is raining, so perhaps Mudje is at home.’

(Gerner 2013: 482)

‘live’

(227) cop cy shyp six qup bop max su **jjox** dde go xi ox.
3P.PL 3P.SG lead RES friend ART = CL-DET live NOM LOC arrive DP

‘He led them to the place where his friend lived.’

(Gerner 2013: 97)

Copula

(228) cyx li shyrx rruo ma nge.

3P.SG TOP thief CL COP

‘He is a thief.’

(Gerner 2013: 178)

42. Yuanjian Kucong 元江苦聪语 (Yuanjiang, Yunnan, China)

Location, existence, possession

mu³³: < ‘sit, dwell’; [animate]

Existential frame

(229) yu³¹ m³³ kh³³ η³¹ tɕue³⁵/mu³³ a³³.

water big in fish there.be PRT

‘There are fishes in the river.’

(Chang 2011: 86)

Possessive frame

- (230) ηa^{31} $z\Lambda^{31}$ $n\epsilon^{33}$ $n\dot{i}^{31}$ vi^{55} $t\epsilon u\epsilon^{35}/mu^{33}$ a^{33} .
 1SG child two CLF have PRT
 ‘I have two children.’ (2011: 87)

Locative frame

- (231) $\gamma\textcircled{3}^{31}$ $z\textcircled{3}^{35}$ mu^{33} ta^{35} $\phi\Lambda^{33}$.
 3SG home be.at DUR AFF.PRT
 ‘It’s certain that he is at home.’
 (Chang Junzhi pers. Comm.)

‘sit’

- (232) ηu^{35} mu^{33} ta^{35} $n\epsilon^{33}$ $kv^{31}li^{31}$ $k^h u\eta^{31}$ li^{31} .
 1PL sit DUR and story tell PRT
 ‘Let’s sit down and tell a story.’
 (Chang 2011: 75)

‘dwell’

- (233) ηa^{31} $tsh\textcircled{3}^{35}$ $n\dot{i}^{31}$ $k^h\textcircled{3}^{31}$ mu^{33} tv^{33} po^{33} .
 1SG here two year live DUR PRF.PRT

‘I having been living here for two year.’

(Chang 2011: 98)

Copula

(234) ɕi³⁵ sv³³ ŋa³⁵ yu³³ zɿ³³.

this book 1SG.POSS POSS COP

‘This book is mine.’

(Chang 2011: 188)

43 Jinuo 基诺语 (Xishuangbanna, Yunnan, China)

tʃɿ^{31/44} (< ‘live’) [animate]

Existential frame

(235) lo³¹mɔ³³ po³¹o⁵⁴ va⁴⁴ ur³¹ thi^{44/33} mɿ⁴⁴ tʃɿ³¹ tɔ⁴⁴ a³³.

stone underside LOC snake one CLF there.be DUR PRT

‘There’s a snake under the stone.’

(Jiang 2010: 246)

Possessive frame

(236) khɿ³¹ ja⁵⁴ zɔ⁴⁴ku⁴⁴ ŋɔ⁴⁴ li⁵⁴ tʃɿ³¹ a³³.

3SG PROP child five CLF have PRT

‘He has five children.’ (Jiang 2010: 245)

Note: Genitive 3SG: khɣ³⁵. The interpretation ‘His five children exists’ is, thus, is not possible.

Locative frame

(237) nΛ³¹ ηu⁵⁴ va⁴⁴ tʃΛ^{31/44} a³³ la^{31?}

2SG where LOC live/be.at PRT PRT

‘Where do you live/Where are you?’

(Jiang 2010: 276)

t[a³¹ [inanimate]]; PROP: proprietive

Existential frame:

(238) khɣ³¹ lΛ⁴⁴khɣ⁴⁴ su³¹tɣ³¹ va⁴⁴ a³³khlo⁴⁴ thi^{44/33} lΛ⁴⁴ tʃa³¹ a³³.

that opposite forest LOC grove.of.bamboo one CLF there.be PRT

‘There’s a grove of bamboo in that forest.’

(Jiang 2010: 246)

Possessive frame

(239) ηo^{31/35} pɔ⁴⁴na³¹ xjo³¹ma⁵⁴ khjy^{44/35} ja⁵⁴vu^{31/35}, ηo³¹ te³³ li³¹ jɔ^{44/31} pɔ⁴⁴na³¹ mΛ⁴⁴ tʃa^{31/35}.

1SG/1SG.POSS buffalo 3PL steal fall because1SG field plough PURP buffalo NEG have
 ‘Because they stole my buffalo, I don’t have any buffalo to plough.’
 (Jiang 2010: 194)

Locative frame

(240) mi³¹tsha⁵⁴ tha⁵⁴la⁵⁴ va⁴⁴ khɔ⁴⁴ tʃʌ^{31/44} khɔ⁴⁴ tʃa³¹ mɣ³³ tʃʌ^{31/44} tɔ⁴⁴ tʃa³¹ tɔ⁴⁴ a³³.
 land upside LOC NOM be.at NOM be.at NOM be.at DUR be.at DUR PRT
 ‘Everything that exists on the earth exists.’
 (Jiang 2010: 160)

Copula

(241) ja⁴⁴tshu⁵⁴ mi³¹tha⁵⁴xo⁴⁴khjɛ⁴⁴ ɲɣ³¹ a⁴⁴ ne³³.
 now raining.season COP PRT PRT
 ‘It’s rainy season now.’
 (Jiang 2010: 251)

44. Bangduo Lahu 邦朵拉祜 (Lancang, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(242) ɲa³¹ ve³³ tso¹¹ qhɔ³³ ɣɔ⁵³tɕi³³ tso³¹.

1SG POSS jar in pickle there.be

‘There’re pickles in my jar.’

(Li 2012: 373)

(243) xɛ³³ qhɔ³³ a³⁵tɕhe⁵³ te⁵³ mo¹¹ tɕhe⁵³.
field in sheep one f lock there.be

‘There’s a flock of sheep in the field.’

(Li 2012: 375)

Possessive frame

(244) nɔ³¹ phu³³ ma⁵³ tso³¹ la⁵³?
2SG money NEG have Q

‘Don’t you have money?’

(Li 2012:170)

Locative frame

(245) thɔ³³la³³tɕi³³ tsho³¹ka³¹ tso³¹.
tractor here be.at

‘The tractor is here.’

(Li 2012: 263)

(246) u³⁵tha⁵³ ŋa³¹ ka³¹ ɔ³¹pa⁵³ tɕhe⁵³ ta¹¹ ve³³ jo³¹.
then 1SG also beside be.at DUR AFF PRT

‘I was certainly on the scene then.’

(Li 2012:69)

‘live’

(247) ɔ³¹yu⁵³sɿ¹¹tha⁵³ ŋa³¹tɛ³¹ yu³¹pu¹¹ tɕhe⁵³ ve³³.
formerly my.family river.bank live PRT

‘My family used to live beside the river’

(Li 2012: 69-70)

Copula

(248) jɔ⁵³ lɛ³³ la⁵³xo¹¹ tsɿ³¹, xɛ⁵³ tsɿ³¹ ma⁵³ xɛ⁵³.
3SG TOP Lahu people Han people NEG COP

‘He is a Lahu, (but) not a Han.’

(Li 2012: 331)

Note: Copula distinct form in negative; zero in positive.

45. Naxi (Lijiang, Yunnan, China)

ndzɿ²¹ [attachement] < ‘sit, dwell’

Existential frame

- (249) t^ha²⁴ ɲji³³ka³³ma³³ a³³ndzə²¹ ɲja²¹ ɲdɯ³³ ɲi³³ndzə²¹ **ndzɿ²¹**.
3SG.POSS yard apricot.tree very big two CLF there.be
‘There’re two big apricot trees in his yard.’
(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Possessive frame

- (250) t^hø³³le³³ he³³tsɿ³³ sə²¹ ɲgɣ³³ ɲdɯ³³ ndzɿ²¹ **ndzɿ²¹**.
rabbit ear long MOD one pair have
‘A rabbit has a pair of long ears.’
(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Locative frame

- (251) he³³k^hɣ⁵⁵ he³³tsɿ²¹ kø⁵⁵ ɣ²¹ **ndzɿ²¹** ja³³.
earring ear on DUR be.at SENS
‘The earring is on the ear.’

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

‘sit’

- (252) xud⁵⁵le²¹ sa³³la²¹ mby²¹ t^he²¹ ndzɿ²¹ jɿ³³.
cat table under DUR sit SENS

The cat sits/squats under the table.

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

‘live’

- (253) ŋɿ²¹ ʒi³³tɕ^hɿ³³ ndzɿ²¹.
1SG Kunming live

‘I live in Kunming.’

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

ʒi³³ [existence inside an entity] < ʒi⁵⁵ ‘lie’

Existential frame

- (254) ze²¹k^hø³³ tɕ^hɿ³³ k^hø³³ pɿ²¹ se²¹, ŋji²¹ mɿ³³ ʒi³³.
well this CLF be.dry PFV water NEG there.be

‘The well is dry and there’s no water.’

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Possessive frame

- (255) [ʰu³³ ci⁵⁵ ŋgy³³, ti⁵⁵we⁵⁵ ŋgy³³ se²¹me³³, pe³³sɿ⁵⁵ ʒi³³ mɤ⁵⁵sɿ³³.
3SG money have social.status have besides capacity have IMPFV
'He is not only rich and of high social standing, but he is of capacity as well.'

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Locative frame

- (256) ŋu²¹ ŋɤ³³ ŋgy³³ ny⁵⁵me³³ lø²¹ ʒi³³.
2SG 1SG POSS heart in be.at
'You're in my heart.'

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

'lie'

- (257) zue²¹ tsua³³ ky³³ t^he²¹ ʒi⁵⁵ jɤ³³.
child bed on DUR lie SENS
'The child is lying/sleeping in the bed.'

(Field Notes, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

ŋgy^{33/21}: general existential verb

ŋgy³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(258) mu³ ky³³ mu³³ky³³mu³³ky⁵⁵ŋji²¹ ŋgy³³ jɣ³³.
sky on rainbow there.be SENS

‘There’s a rainbow in the sky.’

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

(259) mu³³ ky³³ ku²¹ ŋɖu³³ ni³³ly³³ ŋgy³³ jɣ³³.
sky on star one twoCLF there.be SENS

‘There are several stars in the sky.’

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Possessive frame

(260) t^hu³³ zi³³ŋgy³³ndy²¹ ŋu³³ ŋji²¹ ze³³ ndɣ²¹ ŋɖu³³ ŋji²¹ ŋgy³³.
3SG Lijiang at house very big one CLF have

‘He has a big house in Lijiang.’

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Locative frame

(261) k^hua⁵⁵ sa³³la²¹ kɿ³³ ɲgy³³ jɿ³³.

bowl table on be.at SENS

‘The bowl is on the table.’

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

ɲgy²¹ [animate]

Existential frame

(262) ɲɿ⁵⁵-ɲgu²¹ na²¹çi³³ zø³³ ɲgɿ³³ ne⁵⁵, zø³³ p^hu⁵⁵, zø³³ zua³³,

1PL-PL Naxi young.man MOD TOP young.man capable young.man impressive

zø³³ nda²¹ ɲgɿ³³ ɲɖu³³ kɿ⁵⁵ ɲgy²¹, ji⁵⁵ ɿ⁵⁵ji³³nda⁵⁵ mi²¹.

young.man capable MOD one CLF there.be and Ayidan be.named

‘There was a Naxi young man, an impressive, capable and smart young man, called Ayidan.’

(*Ayidan[1]* text, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Possessive frame

(263) ɲɿ²¹ ɲgu³³me³³ ɲɖu³³ kɿ⁵⁵ ɲgy²¹.

1SG younger.sister one CLF have

'I have a younger sister.'

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Locative frame

(264) k^hu³³ k^hu³³mby²¹ pia³³ pia³³ ŋgy²¹ jɣ³³.
dog doghouse side exist SENS

The dog is beside the doghouse.

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

Copula

(265) ŋɣ²¹ sɿ²¹tsɿ³³ wa²¹.

1SG teacher COP

'I'm a teacher.'

(*Field notes*, Shanshan Lü and Yanjuan Mu)

46. Sani 撒尼语 (Shilin, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(266) tɕ'e⁴⁴ o⁴⁴ k'u⁴⁴ ŋæ¹¹ma³³ t'i¹¹ ma⁴⁴ tʂo³³.

village inside street long one CLF there.be

‘There’s a long street in the village.’

(Ma 1951: 119)

Possesive frame

(267) ŋa³³ nɣ⁵⁵ma³³ tʰi¹¹ma⁴⁴ a⁴⁴py³³ tʰi¹¹ma⁴⁴ tʂo³³.

1SG younger.sister one CLF elder.brother one CLF have

‘I have a younger sister and an elder brother.’

(Ma 1951: 119)

(268) kʰi⁴⁴ fɣ⁴⁴ næ³³ sz³³xa³³, a¹¹nɣ⁴⁴ næ³³ ma¹¹ tʂo³³.

3SG husband also die PFV child also NEG have

‘Her husband died and she hasn’t child either.’

(Ma 1951: 87)

(269) ŋa³³ i⁴⁴z³³m³³ ne⁴⁴sz¹¹næ³³ na⁵⁵po⁴⁴ næ³³ ma¹¹ tʂo³³ di¹¹næ³³ a⁴⁴za⁵⁵ ŋa³³ ya¹¹ tʂo³³.

1SG although eye also ear also NEG have but still 1SG strength have

‘Although I don’t have eyes and ears, I still have strength.’

(Ma 1951: 98)

Locative frame

(270) m¹¹sz³³ m³³ tɕ'æ⁴⁴ tʂo³³ la⁵⁵.

god heaven upside be.at DUR

'God is in the heaven.'

(Ma 1951: 88)

(271) ŋa³³ ba¹¹ hæ³³ gu⁴⁴ tʂo³³ la⁵⁵.

1SG father house inside be.at DUR

'My father is at home.'

(Ma 1951: 88)

Locative postposition

(272) k'u⁴⁴ tɕ'æ³³ tʂo³³ qa³³ ʒ³³.

street upside at play go

'go to play in the street'

(Ma 1951: 63)

Copula

(273) ɲa³³ ba¹¹ ẓ⁴⁴ṣẓ⁴⁴ky³³ts'o³³ ɲæ³³.

1SG father carpenter COP

'My father is a carpenter.'

(Ma 1951: 117)

47. Sangkong 桑孔语 (Xishuangbanna, Yunnan, China)

tɕaŋ⁵⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

(274) qhoŋ⁵⁵loŋ⁵⁵ tshaŋ⁵⁵ŋa³¹ tɕaŋ⁵⁵ (ɣ)ŋ³⁵.

inside person there.be PRT

'There's someone inside.'

(Li 2002: 134)

Possessive frame

(275) thaŋ⁵⁵ aŋ³³mboŋ⁵⁵ tɕaŋ⁵⁵ a³³ŋga⁵⁵, the⁵⁵a³³nuŋ³¹ aŋ³³tshi³³ a³¹ tɕaŋ⁵⁵ a³³qaŋ³¹.

3SG elder.brother have although but elder.sister NEG have PRT

'He' has elder brothers but no elder sisters.'

(Li 2002: 172)

Locative frame

(276) thaŋ⁵⁵ tha³³ tɕaŋ⁵⁵.

3SG there be.at

‘He’s over there.’

(Li 2002: 134)

‘live’

(277) na³³ tɕaŋ³³ qha⁵⁵ mbu³¹ zɛ⁵⁵.

here live most good PRT

‘It’s the best (thing) to live here.’

(Li 2002: 188)

Copula

(278) a⁵⁵naŋ³¹ saŋ⁵⁵qhoŋ⁵⁵ ŋgɣ⁵⁵.

1PL Sangkong COP

‘We are Sangkong natives.’

(Li 2002: 137)

48. Woni (Xinping, Yunnan, China)

tso⁵⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

- (279) tsa³³ku³¹ ho⁵⁵ tɔ³³ u⁵⁵to⁵⁵ tso⁵⁵.
grass inside LOC snake there.be
'There's a snake in the grass.'
(Yang 2016: 126)

Possessive frame

- (280) ji⁵⁵ a⁵⁵tɕi³¹ tshɿ³¹ kɔ³¹ tso⁵⁵.
3SG elder.sister one CLF have
'He has an elder sister.'
(Yang 2016: 127)

Note: Genitive 3SG: wa^{13/33} (male); wo⁵⁵ (female) (Yang 2016: 74-75)

Locative frame

- (281) a⁵⁵tɔ⁵⁵ phu³³ tɔ³³ tso⁵⁵ ti⁵⁵.
elder.brother village LOC be.at PRT
'(My) elder brother is in the village.'
(Yang 2016: 126)

'live'

(282) zɔ³¹mɔ⁵⁵ ji⁵⁵ho⁵⁵ zo³³li⁵⁵ thɔ¹³ ɲa⁵³, ha⁵⁵mu⁵⁵mu⁵⁵ tshi³¹ ku³³fu³¹çi⁵⁵nɛ³³ tso⁵⁵ tshi³¹ ɲa⁵³.
that house old one PRT well VCLF mend then live can PRT

'That's an old house. One can live in only after well mending it.'

(Yang 2016: 79)

tɕa³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(283) hɔ⁵⁵lo³¹ tɔ³³ i⁵⁵tshu³¹ tɕa³³.
field LOC water there.be

'There's water in the field.'

(Yang 2016: 126)

Possessive frame

(284) ɲɔ⁵⁵ ku³¹pa³³ tɕa³³ ti⁵⁵.
1SG money have PRT

'I have money.'

(Yang 2016: 127)

(285) tsho⁵⁵ i⁵⁵hu³¹hu³¹ tshɿ³¹ kɔ³¹ tshɔ⁵⁵mɔ⁵⁵ tsu³¹ji⁵⁵ tsa³³ tshi³¹.
 person little one CLF what idea have can
 ‘What ideas such a little person can have!’ (Rhetorical)
 (Yang 2016: 247)

Locative frame

(286) hɔ⁵⁵to³¹ hɔ⁵⁵phi³¹ tɛ³³ ji⁵⁵ho⁵⁵ wa¹³ tɔ³³ tsa³³ ti⁵⁵.
 field land TOP house underside LOC be.at PRT
 ‘The field and land are below the house.’
 (Yang 2016: 158)

Copula

(287) ji⁵⁵ lɔ³¹ku⁵⁵ ju⁵⁵ ti⁵⁵.
 3 Lolo COP PRT
 ‘He is a Lolo.’
 (Yang 2016: 123)

49. Kaduo Hani (Mojiang, Yunnan, China)

tsa³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(288) mi³¹ ɔ³³ ɲe³¹tɕhi³¹ a⁵⁵ɲu⁵⁵ ei³¹ ma³¹ tsã³⁵.
sky LOC cloud a.little even NEG there.be

‘There isn’t even a cloud in the sky.’

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 70)

Note: tsa³³ can be nasalized when it occupies the sentence-final position (Zhao and Zhu 2011: 69).

Possessive frame

(289) ɲɔ⁵⁵ ɲɔ³¹ mu³¹ xɔ⁵⁵ tsa³³ ei⁵⁵.
1SG five UNIT field have PRT

‘I have a field of five mus.’

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 69)

Note: Genitive 1SG: ɲɔ³³ (Zhao and Zhu 2011: 24)

Locative frame

(290) ka³¹tɕhi³¹ ɕã̃³³tsɿ³¹ tɕhi⁵⁵lɔ⁵⁵ ɔ³³ tsa³³.
clothes chest inside LOC be.at

‘The clothes are in the chest.’

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 69)

tso⁵⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

- (291) a³¹ŋi⁵⁵lɔ⁵⁵ ɔ³³ khu³¹ tsõ⁵⁵.
outside LOC dog there.be
'There's a dog outside.'

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 70)

Note: tso⁵⁵ can be nasalized when it occupies the sentence-final position (Zhao and Zhu 2011: 69).

Possessive frame

- (292) ʒɔ³¹xɔ³¹ ʒa³¹mi³¹ tu³¹ thu³¹ kɔ³¹ tsõ⁵⁵.
3SG daughter only one CLF have
'He has only one daughter.'

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 70)

Locative frame

- (293) ʒɔ³¹xɔ³¹ ʒi⁵⁵khɔ⁵⁵ ɔ³³ ma³¹ tso⁵⁵, pɣ³¹pɣ³¹ me⁵⁵ ʒo²¹.
3SG house LOC NEG be.at in.vain ADV walk

‘He’s not at home, and I went there in vain.’

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 216)

Copula

(294) ʒɔ³¹xɔ³¹ a⁵⁵tɕhi³³ʒɔ³¹ ɲɤ⁵⁵.

3SG orphan COP

‘He’s an orphan.’

(Zhao and Zhu 2011: 71)

50. Biyue Hani 碧约哈尼语 (Mojiang Biyue, Yunnan, China)

tsu³³ [animate]

Existential frame

(295) jɪ⁵⁵kho⁵⁵ a³³ tshu⁵⁵ mɔ³¹ tsu³³.

house LOC person NEG there.be

‘There’s no person in the house.’

(Jing 2015: 66)

Possessive frame

(296) ɲa⁵⁵ ɲi⁵⁵tɕɿ³¹ mɔ³¹ tsu³³.

1SG sibling NEG have

‘I don’t have siblings.’

(Jing 2015: 67)

Locative frame

(297) a³³mɔ³³ po³³to³¹ a³¹ tsu³³ e³³.

mother kitchen LOC be.at PRT

‘Mom is in the kitchen.’

(Jing 2015: 66)

tsa³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(298) tsɔ³³tsɿ³³ tsa³³ thi³¹ti⁵⁵ thu³¹ pə³¹ tsa³³.

table on key one CLF there.be

‘There’s a key on the table.’

(Jing 2015: 67)

Possessive frame

(299) ji³¹khɔ³¹ tɕhɤŋ31 ma³¹ tsa³³.

3SG.NOM money NEG have

‘He doesn’t have money.’

(Jing 2015: 66)

(300) ji³¹khɔ³¹ ma³³tsɿ³³ ji³³mɔ³³thur³¹ tui³³ tsa³³.

3SG.NOM eye big one pair have

‘She has a pair of big eyes.’

(Jing 2015: 66)

(301) ŋa⁵⁵ nɔ³¹ ji³³mi³³tsu³¹ kur³¹ tʂhɿ³¹ ma³¹ tsa³³.

1SG.NOM 2SG.ACC want REL medicine NEG have

‘I don’t have the medicine that you want.’

(Jing 2015: 67)

Locative frame

(302) sɔ³¹kɔ³¹ tʂa³³tʂa³³ tsa³³.

book shelf be.at

‘The book is on the shelf.’

(Jing 2015: 66)

Copula

- (303) ji³¹khɔ³¹ ηɔ³³ kuɯ³³ a⁵⁵kɔ³³ ηe³³/ηuɯ³³.
3SG.NOM 1SG.POSS POSS elder.brother COP
'He's my elder brother.'
(Jing 2015: 65)

Note: When the copular complement is determined or modified by the first-person pronoun, the variant of the copula ηe³³, ηuɯ³³, can be used (Jing 2015: 65)

51. Akha 阿卡语 (Mae Sui, Chiang Rai, Thailand)

dzɔ⁵⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

- (304) ηjum⁵⁵ la³¹xɔ⁵⁵ tshɔ⁵⁵xa³¹ ø³¹ ya³¹ dzɔ⁵⁵.
house inside people four CLF there.be
'There're four people in the house.'
(Dai 2009: 159)

Possessive frame

- (305) ηa⁵⁵ a³¹jɣ³¹ a³¹ηji⁵⁵ ma³¹ dzɔ⁵⁵.

1SG Y.brother E.brother NEG have

'I don't have siblings.'

(Dai 2009: 92)

Locative frame

(306) ɲa⁵⁵ pa³¹gɲɲ³¹ ɲɲ⁵⁵ dzo⁵⁵ e³³.

1SG Beijing LOC be.at PRT

'I'm in Beijing.'

(Dai 2009: 127)

'live'

(307) ɲa⁵⁵ ta³¹bo⁵⁵va³³vi³³ ɲɲ⁵⁵ dzo⁵⁵ e³³.

1SG county Wanwei_{PLACENAME} LOC live PRT

'I live in Wanwei county.'

(Dai 2009: 127)

gja³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(308) tu⁵⁵ ɲ³³ la³¹xø⁵⁵ xum³¹ma³¹ thi³¹ ma³¹ gjä³³ si³¹.

cupboard POSS inside bowl one CLF there.be still

‘There’s still a bowl in the cupboard.’

(Dai 2009: 97)

Possessive frame

(309) η⁵⁵ sa³¹η³³ thi³¹ gu³³ **gja³³** η³³.

1SG shoe one pair have PRT

‘I have a pair of shoes.’

(Dai 2009: 97)

Note: Genitive 1SG: η³¹η³³. When genitive forms are used with kinship terms, η³³ can be absent but the tones of pronouns change (Dai 2009: 131).

Locative frame

(310) η³¹η³³ ηjum⁵⁵ tsa³¹ua⁵⁵dze³¹xa³¹ ηη⁵⁵ ma³¹ **gja³³**.

2SG.POSS home Chiang.Rai LOC NEG be.at

‘Your home is not in Chiang Rai.’

(Dai 2009: 201)

Copula

(311) a³¹η³¹ na⁵⁵a³¹ khu⁵⁵ me³³, sηη³¹bo³¹dzɔ³³ja³¹ ma³¹ **ηη⁵⁵**.

3SG TOP teacher PRT student NEG COP

‘He’s a teacher but not a student.’

(Dai 2009: 95)

52. Cosao 搓梭语 (Mengla, Yunnan, China)

tɕa³³ [inanimate]

Existential frame

(312) tso⁵⁵ ə³¹u⁵³ a³¹ suw³¹tsu⁵⁵ ŋje⁵³ po⁵⁵ tɕa³³ a³³.
house front LOC tree two CLF have PRT

‘There’re two trees in front of the house.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 184)

Possessive frame

(313) ŋɔ⁵⁵ phju⁵⁵ ma³¹ tɕa³³.
1SG money NEG have

‘I don’t have money.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 211)

Note: 1SG.GEN: ŋə³¹(ə³³) (Bai et al. 2015: 84)

Locative frame

(314) nɛ⁵⁵ a³¹pa⁵³ tso⁵⁵ khə³¹pa³³ tɕa³³?

2SG Y.brother house where be.at

‘Where’s your younger brother’s house?’

(Bai et al. 2015: 108)

tɕo⁵⁵/tɕu⁵⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

(315) lo⁵⁵tshi⁵³ a³³ ηə³¹tə⁵⁵ tɕo⁵⁵ py⁵⁵ ə³³.

river LOC fish there.be many PRT

‘There’re many fishes in the river.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 185)

Possessive frame

(316) ηə⁵⁵γu³³ pu³¹na³³ tɕo⁵⁵ py⁵⁵ ə³³.

1PL cattle have very PRT

‘We have many cattle.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 185)

Locative frame

(317) a³³zau⁵³ tso⁵⁵min⁵⁵ a³³ tɕo⁵⁵ ə³³.

E.brother village LOC be.at PRT

‘(My) elder brother is in the village.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 185)

‘live’

(318) ŋə³³yu³¹ za³¹ tɕo³³ ə³³.

1PL here live PRT

‘We live here.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 268)

Copula

(319) ŋə⁵⁵yu³³ tsho⁵⁵sɔ⁵⁵ma⁵³ ma³¹ ŋu⁵⁵.

1PL Cosao.people NEG COP

‘We aren’t Cosao.’

(Bai et al. 2015: 187)

53. Azha 阿扎语 (Wenshan, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(320) ku⁵⁵li⁵⁵ zɛ³³ ŋo³³ tʂhu²¹ tʂu²¹.

there chicken five six there be

‘There’re five or six chickens.’

(Li 2011: 48)

Possessive frame

(321) nɛ²¹ zo³³ ɬi⁵⁵ vi³³, zɛ³³mɛ³³ si⁵⁵ vi³³ tʂu²¹.

1PL son four CLF daughter three CLF have

‘We have four sons and three daughter.’

(Li 2011: 49)

Locative frame

(322) ŋa⁵⁵ mo³³ i²¹ku⁵⁵ tʂu³⁵.

1SG mother inside be.at

‘My mother is inside.’

(Li 2011: 39)

‘live’

- (323) $\eta\alpha^{21}$ $i^{21}p\ae^{33}$ ta^{33} $phie^{33}$ phe^{55} **$t\mathfrak{s}u^{35}$** .
 1SG river opposite.side live
 ‘I live across the river.’
 (Li 2011: 40)

Copula

- (324) he^{21} $t\epsilon ie^{55}$ ti^{33} he^{21} ko^{55} vi^{33} he^{21} **no^{51}** .
 house this one CLF 3SG family house COP
 ‘This house is the house of his family’s.’
 (Li 2011: 44)

54. Nusu 怒族语 (Nujiang, Yunnan, China)

ηi^{35} [animate]

Existential frame

- (325) i^{31} $g\iota\alpha^{53}$ do^{35} $\eta\alpha^{55}$ **ηi^{35}** α^{31} .
 water LOC fish there.be PRT
 ‘There’re fishes in the water.’
 (Sun and Liu 1986: 69)

Possessive frame

(326) ʔnɔ⁵⁵ zɑ⁵⁵ sɔ³⁵ ʔiɥ⁵³ ni³⁵ ɑ³¹.
3SG child three CLF have PRT

‘He has three children.’

(Sun and Liu 1986: 68)

Note: Genitive 3SG: ʔne⁵⁵(e³¹) ‘his’

Locative frame

(327) ŋɑ³⁵ iɔ³⁵ ni³⁵ dʒɑ³¹ dɣ⁵⁵!
1SG home be.at PRT PRT

‘I’m at home!’

(Sun and Liu 1986: 86)

Copula

(328) ɕi³⁵ ku³¹ piɔ⁵³khue³⁵ uã⁵³ lɛ³¹ mɑ⁵⁵ uã⁵³ ɕi⁵⁵?
this CLF pen COP or NEG COP PRT

‘Is this one a pen or not?’

(Sun and Liu 1986: 88)

‘sit’

(329) **ni**³⁵ ‘sit’

(Sun and Liu 1986: 160)

‘live’

(330) **ni**³⁵ ‘live’

(Sun and Liu 1986:161)

55. Zauzou 柔若语 (Nujiang, Yunnan, China)

ni³³ [animate]

Existential frame

(331) la³³pi⁵⁵ tɕo⁵⁵ ku⁵⁵ ŋo³³ **ni**³³ .
river CLF in fish there.be

‘There’re fishes in the river.’

(Sun et al. 2002: 92)

Possessive frame

(332) ŋu⁵⁵ zo³¹ nɛ⁵³ ia⁵³ **ni**³³ .
1SG child two CLF have

'I have two children.'

(Sun et al. 2002: 92)

Locative frame

(333) uɛ⁵⁵! ɲu⁵⁵ ʔa⁵⁵ka⁵⁵ ɲi³³ tɔ̃⁵³!

hey 1SG here be.at DUR

'Hey! I'm here!'

(Sun et al. 2002: 133)

'sit'

(334) ɲi³³ tɔ̃⁵³ pɛ̃⁵³

sit MAN play.(instrument)

'play (instrument) in manner of sitting'

(Sun et al. 2002: 98)

'live'

(335) ɲu⁵⁵ ni³³ ɲo³³ tu³¹pa⁵³ yi³³tshe⁵⁵ ɲe⁵⁵ ɲi³³ zɔ̃³¹.

1SG and 2SG together forty year live PFV

'You and me have been living together for 40 years.'

(Sun et al. 2002: 128)

Copula

- (336) tu⁵⁵ la³³tɕa³³ tsha⁵⁵pɔ³³za⁵⁵su⁵⁵ ʔa³¹ ɲɛ⁵³, ʔa⁵⁵se⁵³ tsha⁵⁵pɔ³³za⁵⁵su⁵⁵ ɲɛ⁵³ zɔ³¹.
3SG before student NEG COP now student COP COS
'He wasn't a student, but he is now.'

(Sun et al. 2002: 149)

56. Khatso 卡卓语 (Yuxi, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

- (337) tsɣ²⁴tsɿ³¹ mɛ³³ ka⁵⁵ tsɿ³¹ tɛ³¹ pɣ⁵³ tso³²³.
table CLF upside liquor one jar there.be
'There's a jar of liquor on the table.'

(Mu 2002: 118)

Possessive frame

- (338) ɲa³³ sv⁵⁵pɛ³¹ tɛ³¹ pɛ³¹ tso²⁴ zɑ³³.
1SG book one CLF have PRT
'I have a book.'

(Mu 2002: 115)

Locative frame

- (339) su⁵⁵pe³¹pe³¹ xa³³ŋa⁵⁵ tso²⁴ ŋa³¹?
book CLF where be.at PRT
'Where is the book?'

(Mu 2002: 84)

Possessive frame

- (340) ŋa³³ nɛ³³ ŋa⁵⁵ kur³¹ ŋa³¹ ma³¹ ta³²³, ʒi³³wɛ²⁴ ŋa³³ sa²⁴ke³³ tɛ³³ tɕi³³ tso³²³ ŋɛ³¹.
1SG 2SG lend give PRT NEG can because 1SG only one CLF have PRT
'I can't lend it to you, because I only have one.'

(Mu 2002: 60)

Copula

- (341) ji³³ ŋa⁵⁵ sɛ³³ pa³¹ (ŋɛ³³).
3SG 1SG family father COP
'He's my father.'

(Dai et al. 1987: 264)

57. Lashi 勒期语 (Dehong, Yunnan, China)

ɲje:i⁵³ [animate]

Existential frame

(342) pɔm⁵³ mo³³ no³³ ta⁵³ tu³³ **ɲje:i⁵³** tɔ³³.
hill LOC cow one CLF there.be DUR

‘There’s a cow on the hill.’

(Dai and Li 2007: 228)

(343) ɲo⁵³ jɔm³³ mo³³ kjɔŋ³¹ ta⁵³ tu³³ **ɲje:i⁵³**.
1SG family LOC chicken one CLF there.be

‘There’s a chicken in my house.’

(Dai and Li 2007: 175)

Possessive frame

(344) naŋ⁵³nuŋ⁵⁵ jɔm³³ vuŋ³¹ khǎ³³mjo⁵³ tu³³ **ɲje:i⁵³?**
2PL family pig how.many CLF have

‘How many pigs does your family have?’

(Dai and Li 2007: 117)

Locative frame

(345) ɲo⁵³ maŋ⁵³ŋ⁵³ mo³³ ɲje:i⁵³.

1SG Mangshi_{PLACENAME} LOC be.at

‘I’m in Mangshi.’

(Dai and Li 2007: 174)

ɲɔ:⁵³ [interior]

Existential frame

(346) ɲɔn³³ mo³³ ɲji³³ ək⁵⁵ khjap⁵⁵ tsa³³ ɲɔ:⁵³.

cupboard LOC coat two CLF only there.be

‘There’re only two coats in the cupboard.’

(Dai and Li 2007: 229)

Possessive frame

(347) ɲjaŋ³³ jɔm³³ ɲɔ:⁵³ tək³¹ ɲje³³.

3SG strength have extremely PRT

‘He has great strength.’

(Dai and Li 2007: 229)

Locative frame

- (348) pji³³mei⁵³ pɔn³³ mo³³ pɔ:⁵³ tɔ³³.
clothes cupboard LOC be.at DUR
'The clothes are in the cupboard.'
(Dai and Li 2007: 229)

- (349) no³³ khɔm³³ mə³¹ lu:ŋ⁵⁵ tɔ⁵⁵.
cattle pen in be.at DUR
'The cow is in the pen.'
(Dai and Li 2007: 19)

Note: lu:ŋ⁵⁵ < 'live' (Dai and Li 2007: 317 [item 1678])

Copula

- (350) ŋa⁵⁵ jɔm³³ ke³³ lu³³ji⁵⁵ mo³³ ŋu:t⁵⁵.
1SG.POSS family TOP Luxi_{PLACENAME} LOC COP
'My hometown is Luxi.'
(Dai and Li 2007: 175)

- (351) nap^{31jɔ} ɲjei⁵⁵ mɔ⁵³ ɲo⁵³ ke³³ sə³³ ʒa³³ ɲɔt⁵⁵ pje³³.
 tomorrow ABL 1SG TOP teacher COP PFV
 ‘From tomorrow, I’ll be a teacher.’
 (Dai and Li 2007: 176)

58. Yadu Qiang 雅都羌语 (Yadu, Sichuan, China)

zi [animate]

Existential frame

- (352) səf-tho-zgu-ta wətshi-o-u zi.
 tree-that:one-CL-LOC sparrow-one-CL exist
 ‘There is a sparrow in that tree.’
 (LaPolla and Huang 2003: 134)

Possessive frame

- (353) khumtsi tutʂ-ɣzə-zi zi-z.
 Khumtsi younger.brother-four-CL exist-CAUS
 ‘Khumtsi has four younger brothers.’
 (LaPolla and Huang 2003: 98)

Locative frame

(354) bəiχa tʂuatsə-le:-ʂqəl-la zi.

housefly table-DEF:CL-under-LOC exist

‘A fly is under the table.’

(LaPolla and Huang 2003: 107)

ʂə [inanimate]

Existential frame

(355) tʂuats-məq-ta ləyz-e-pen ʂə.

table-top-LOC book-one-CL exist

‘There is a book on the table.’

(LaPolla and Huang 2003: 133)

Possessive frame

(356) khumtsi dzəgʷ kən ɑ-ha ʂə-z.

Khumtsi money very one-pl exist-CAUS

‘Khumtsi has a lot of money.’

(LaPolla and Huang 2003: 98)

Locative frame

- (357) ʔũ-panə-la-ha tsa **sə-san**.
2sg-key-DEN:ONE-pl here exist-2sgU
'Your things are here.'
(LaPolla and Huang 2003: 148)

Copula

- (358) the: sum-ke-ze (or -ke:) **ŋuə**.
3SG teacher-INDEF-CL COP
'He is a teacher.'
(LaPolla and Huang 2003: 61)

59. Longxi Qiang 龙溪羌语 (Longxi, Sichuan, China)

jì [animate]

Existential frame

- (359) dàqéí mù=kà à-kò **jì** wé.
previously person=INDEF one-CL.family EXIST ATT
'Previously there was a family.' (T9)
(Zheng 2016: 143)

Possessive frame

- (360) tçi à-wò = sákè **jì** = pù wé.
son one-CL = only EXIST = HET ATT
'(The old couple) only had a son.' (T14)
(Zheng 2016: 143)

- (361) tsùtsú ts^hè-wó **tsé** pà pù = sè wè.
child three-CL have become do = 2SG:PFV ATT
'(You (SG)) have three children now.' (T7)
(Zheng 2016: 315)

'catch'

- (362) ɸà **tsé**
fish catch
'catch fish'
(Zheng 2016: 631)

Locative frame

(363) dù pù-mù tçǎn-tçè ánə = χè jì wé?
ghost do-NOM this:PL-CL.HB where = LOC EXIST ATT
‘Where are these people who can change into ghosts?’ (T11:7)
(Zheng 2016: 342)

‘stand’

(364) tə-jì!
UP-stand
‘(You (SG)) stand up!’
(Zheng 2016: 366)

‘live’

(365) peijì piàto = tì tçá = jí = ə' wè.
now Paduo = DEF CON = EXIST = HS ATT
‘(I heard) (Yu Cheng) is still living in Paduo (Village).’ (CV1)
(Zheng 2016: 143)

Copula

(366) qà lán tçátù ηù = sà wé.

1SG ATT(CH) girl COP = 1SG:PFV ATT

‘I was a girl.’

(Zheng 2016: 446)

60. Guiqiong 贵琼语 (Kangding, Sichuan, China)

nã³⁵ [animate]

Existential frame

(367) ti⁵⁵gã⁵³ xu³³tɕa³³ mũ³⁵ ka³³la⁵³ nã³⁵, ts^hɛ⁵⁵tsə³³ ka³³la⁵³ jẽ⁵⁵.

à ce moment rue personne beaucoup exister voiture beaucoup exister

‘A ce moment-là, il y avait beaucoup de gens dans la rue et ainsi il y avait beaucoup de voitures.’

(Rao 2015: 356)

Possessive frame

(368) ŋə³³ gwi³⁵tɕ^hi³³ mɔ³³-nã⁵⁵.

1SG wife NEG-have

‘I don’t have a wife.’

(Rao 2017: 90)

Locative frame/‘live’

(369) $\eta\text{ə}^{33}$ $\text{Ndz}\tilde{\text{e}}^{33}\text{-k}\tilde{\text{e}}^{53}$ $\text{n}\tilde{\text{a}}^{35}$.
 1SG chinois-endroit exister/habiter
 ‘Je suis dans la région chinoise.’
 ‘J’habite dans la region chinoise.’
 (Rao 2015: 426, 280)

$\text{j}\tilde{\text{e}}^{55}$ [inanimate]

Existential frame

See (366).

Possessive frame

(370) $\text{j}\text{ɔ}^{35}\text{tsi}^{33}$ $\text{ɕ}\text{e}^{33}\text{-wu}^{53}$: “ wu^{53} $\text{d}\tilde{\text{e}}^{33}\eta\tilde{\text{e}}^{53}$ $\text{j}\tilde{\text{e}}^{55}$.”
 singe dire-NMLZ LOG idée exister
 ‘Le singe dit: “j’ai une idée.”’
 (Rao 2015: 359)

Locative frame

(371) $\text{j}\text{w}\tilde{\text{a}}^{33}\text{t}\text{ʂ}\text{ə}^{53}$ $\text{k}^{\text{h}}\text{a}^{53}$ $\text{z}\text{ə}^{35}$ $\text{Ng}\text{a}^{33}\text{li}^{33}$ $\text{j}\tilde{\text{e}}^{55}$.
 river CLF hill back be.at

‘The river is behind the hill.’

(Min Rao pers. comm.)

bu³⁵ [inalienable]

Existential frame

(372) ũ³³pu⁵⁵-gu⁵³ xwi⁵⁵ ji³³ p^ha⁵³ bu³⁵.
mouth-LOC tooth two CLF there.be

‘There’re two teeth in the mouth.’

(Min Rao pers. comm.)

Possessive frame

(373) ti³³ ge³⁵mũ⁵⁵ p^hə⁵³ xwi⁵⁵ p^ha⁵³ ji⁵⁵ mə³³-bu³⁵.
ce femme âgée CLF:GENERAL dent CLF:OBJET même NEG-exister

‘Cette femme âgée n’a même pas de dents.’

(Rao 2015: 301)

Locative frame

(374) xwi⁵⁵ ji³³ p^ha⁵³ ũ³³pu⁵⁵-gu⁵³ bu³⁵.
tooth two CLF mouth-LOC be.at

‘The two teeth are in the mouth.’

(Min Rao pers. comm.)

Copula

(375) $\eta\text{ə}^{33}\text{-m}\tilde{\text{e}}^{55}$ $\text{m}\tilde{\text{i}}^{33}\text{ts}^{\text{h}\text{ɔ}^{33}}$ $\text{t}\text{ɕ}\text{d}^{55}\text{t}^{\text{h}\text{ə}^{55}}\text{ts}^{\text{h}\text{ə}^{55}}\text{li}^{55}$ $\text{dz}\text{ə}^{35}$.

1SG-GEN nom Gya-theg-mtho-legs être

‘Mon nom est Gya-theg-mtho-legs.’

(Rao 2015: 542)

61. Tujia 土家语 (Longshan, Hunan, China)

ɕe^{35} [positive]

Existential frame

(376) kai^{35} $\text{kha}^{21}\text{mo}\eta^{21}$ $\text{ka}^{21}\text{xa}^{35}$ $\text{ɲie}^{35}\text{pi}^{55}$ ɲie^{55} $\text{lo}\eta^{55}$ ɕie^{35} .

this tree upside bird two CLF there.be

‘There’re two birds in the tree.’

(Chen 2006: 57)

Possessive frame

(377) ko^{35} $\text{no}^{55}\text{pi}^{21}$ ne^{55} $\text{a}^{55}\text{xu}^{55}$ ɕe^{35} .

3SG son two CLF have

'He has two sons.'

(Tian et al. 1986: 65)

Locative frame

(378) tsh⁵⁵phi⁵⁵ s²¹thie³⁵ ka²¹ **ɕe³⁵**.

book table upside be.at

'The book is on the table.'

(Meiyan Lu pers. comm.)

thai³⁵ [negative]

Existential frame

(379) wu³⁵ tshi²¹ **thai³⁵**.

burn NMLZ not.there.be

'There's nothing to burn (/there's no firewoods).'

(Tian et al. 1986: 92)

Possessive frame

(380) ki⁵⁵tse⁵⁵ wu³⁵ni²¹ka²¹ **thai³⁵**.

3PL cow not.have

‘They don’t have cows.’

(Tian et al. 1986: 65)

Locative frame

(381) ai¹di¹ biu² ku¹za⁴ ga³ha² tai².
ai⁵⁵ti⁵⁵ tiu²⁴ khu⁵⁵t⁵⁵sa⁵¹ ka²¹xa²⁴ thai²⁴
that girl hills top not.have

‘The girl is not on the hills.’

(Brassett et al 2006: 54)

(382) tsh⁵⁵phi⁵⁵ s²¹thie³⁵ ka²¹ kau⁵³ la²¹.
book table upside be.at CONT

‘The book is on the table.’

(Meiyan Lu pers. comm.)

‘do’

(383) ni³⁵ tɕhie⁵³ kau⁵³ la²¹?
2SG what do CONT

‘What are you doing?’

(Meiyan Lu pers. comm.)

Copula

(384) ko³⁵ me³⁵ tçiã⁵⁵ siu³⁵.

3SG bamboo.strip craftsman COP

‘He’s a bamboo strip craftsman.’

(Tian et al. 1986: 66)

62. Drung 独龙语 (Gongshan, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(385) sa⁵⁵ɿa⁵⁵ mu³¹dãm⁵³ dɔ³¹ pu³¹ŋa⁵³ kɿŭ⁵⁵ puŋ⁵⁵ dʒi⁵⁵je⁵⁵ ǎl⁵³.

table upside LOC five six CLF book there.be

‘There’re five or six books on the table.’

(Sun 1982: 58)

Possessive frame

(386) ti⁵⁵ʒɿ⁵⁵ min⁵⁵da⁵⁵ ti⁵⁵klɔŋ⁵³ ǎl⁵³.

one.CLF gun one.CLF have

‘Each (person) has a gun.’

(Sun 1982: 67)

Locative frame

(387) pu³¹tsǎ⁵⁵ mu³¹kuŋ⁵⁵ sep⁵⁵ dɔ³¹ ǎi⁵³.
sieve fire.pit front LOC be.at

‘The sieve is in front of the fire pit.’

(Sun 1982: 54)

Copula

(388) kǎ⁵⁵ cǔm⁵³ li⁵⁵su⁵⁵ ǎi⁵³ cǔm⁵³ e⁵³.
that house Lisu.people be.at house COP

‘That house is the one that Lisu people stay in.’

(Sun 1982: 75)

63. Jingpho (Kachin) 景颇语 (Dehong, Yunnan, China)

ʒoŋ³³ [interior]

Existential frame

(389) kha^{ʔ31}khon³¹ e³¹ ŋa⁵⁵ ʒoŋ³³ ai³³.

ditch LOC fish there.be IND.3SG.STAT

‘There’re fishes in the ditch.’

(Dai 2012: 102)

Possessive frame

(390) naŋ³³ ko³¹ n³¹kun³¹ wa³³mi³³ tʃau³³ ko³¹ ʒoŋ³³ ŋa³¹ n³¹tai³³.
2SG TOP strength INTJ though TOP have CONT IND.2SG.STAT

‘You have strength though.’

(Dai 2012: 428)

Locative frame

(391) lai³¹ka³³ sum⁵⁵pu⁵⁵ tha³¹ ʒoŋ³³ ai³³.
book box inside be.in IND.3SG.STAT

‘The book is in the box.’

(Dai 2012)

ŋa³¹

Existential frame

(392) n³³tai³³ pa³³e³¹ kat⁵⁵ la⁵⁵ŋai⁵¹ mi³³ ʃa³¹ ŋa³¹ ai³³.

this basin street one one only there.be IND.3SG.STAT

‘There’s only one market in this basin.’

(Dai 2012: 120)

Locative frame

(393) nu⁵¹ n⁵⁵ta⁵⁵ ŋa³¹ ai³³.

mother home be.at IND.3SG.STAT

‘Mother is at home.’

(Dai 2012: 102)

‘live’

(394) ʃi³³ ŋa³¹ ai³³ ko⁷⁵⁵ sa³³ tam³³ uʔ³¹!

3SG live REL place go look.for 2SG.IMP

‘Go to the place where he lives to look for him!’

(Dai 2012: 63)

Possessive frame

(395) ŋai³³ ŋa³³ la⁵⁵ŋai⁵¹ mi³³ lu³¹ n³¹ŋai³³

1SG oxc one one have IND.1SG.STAT

‘I have an ox.’

(Dai 2012 :103)

‘obtain’

(396) lu³¹ ‘obtain’

(Liu 1984: 108)

(397) ʃi³³ ko³¹ ŋai⁵⁵ nau³³ ʒe⁵⁵ ai³³.
3SG TOP 1SG Y.brother COP IND.3SG.STAT

‘He is my younger brother.’

(Dai 2012: 104)

64. Turung (Assam, India)

Existential frame

(398) numnang ngkhong nga de
num³nan³ ŋ¹khon² ŋaa² de¹
[friend two] have REAL

‘There were two friends.’

(Morey 2010: 537)

Possessive frame

- (399) kchi mu nga kchi kchi
kəcii³ muu¹ **ŋaa²** kəcii³ kəcii³
[small]_{NP} also have [small.REDUPL]_{NP}
'I also have chicks, small ones.'
(Morey 2010: 304)

- (400) ngai na ksa mli nga
ŋai³ naa³ kəsaa² məlii³ **ŋaa²**.
1SG POSS child four have
'I have four children.'
(Morey 2010: 539)

Locative frame

- (401) sngoih theyng nga da de
səŋoi³ theeŋ³ **ŋaa²** daa² de¹
long ago PL live KEEP REAL
'Long ago we were there.'

(Morey 2010: 412)

‘live’

- (402) gai kthet na yong nga n- ngut hah.
gai³ kəthet³ naa³ yon² ɲaa² n³- ɲut¹ haʔ¹
very hot SEQ when live NEG- able DECL
‘If it is very hot, we cannot live.’

(Morey 2010: 134)

Copula

- (403) ngai na kphu samko wa
ɲai³ naa³ kə-phuu² sam³koo³ waa¹
[1SG POSS AR-EL.BR]_{CC} [PN DEF]_{CS}
‘My elder brother is Sam Ko.’

(Morey 2010: 533)

65. Karen Geba (Thandaung, Karen, Myanmar)

Existential frame

- (404) dó dó bú nò bjà ʔə̄ ɛ̄bwè t̄ə tʰə̄ʔ

at village in that person have CLF one thousand

‘There are one thousand people in the village.’

(Shee 2008: 82)

Possessive frame

(405) ɓé jè ʔò jə ʃibùp^hábúp^hò əlèkánù dʒʔ jè ʔò kī jəp^hòjəli jə sàʔi ɓè jəp^hòjəli
when 1s have 1s family after and 1s have and my children 1s take care have to my children

‘After I had a family, I had to take care of my children.’

(Shee 2008: 173-174)

(406) sə ʃi ʔò θó wà
3s house have three CLF

‘He has three houses.’

(Shee 2008: 129)

Locative frame

(407) sə ʔò wè dó máŋdǎlé
3s stay still at Mandalay

‘He is still in Mandalay.’

(Shee 2008: 49)

- (408) t^hwì ʔò jì lè?
dog live house under
'The dog is under the house.'
(Shee 2008: 213)

'live'

- (409) nā-mò-nā-pà ʔò ēlò nù ʔò ɓò
2s-mother-2s-father stay place this stay IMP
'Stay where your parents live.'
(Shee 2008: 140)

Copula

- (410) sè mī sārà
3s be teacher
PRN COP N
'He is a teacher'
(Shee 2008: 47)

66. Eastern Kayah LI (Mae Hong Son, Thailand)

Existential frame

- (411) dīpə ʔo təmē too|| pē ʔo phé təmē too too
pot exist one-C:large bottle exist only one-C:large RDP

‘There’s only one pot; and only one bottle as well.’

(Solnit 1997: 230)

Possessive frame

- (412) vē rū ʔo sō ba
1s silver exist three baht

‘I have three baht.’

(Solnit 1997: 10)

Locative frame

- (413) pənè [cwi ʔithá pā] ʔo tōútē
buffalo pull plough IRR exist where

‘Where’s the buffalo that will pull the plow?’

(Solnit 1997: 228)

'live'

- (414) ?a phā nΛ ?o dʒ hi thū hú pe ?o ?ā nΛ
3 grandmother NØ exist at:U house edge as 1p exist this NØ
'His grandmother lived at the edge of the village, like we live here.'
(Solnit 1997: 225)

Copula

- (415) MīΛ nΛ **ma** vē phē mē
(name) TOP be.so 1S father EXCL
'Mi'a is my father!'
(Solnit 1997: 239)

67. Daai Chin (Kanpetlet, Chin State, Myanmar)

Existential frame

- (416) Ahlaanüŋ msü am **ve** ha:m.
Long.ago rice.wine.pot NEG there.be ASP:yet
'Long ago rice wine pots did not yet exist.'
(So-Hartmann 2009: 213)

Possessive frame

- (417) Sheen Phäih = a veei: me: kphyü-kip **ve** = kti.
Sheen Phäih = GEN place goat forty have = NON.FUT
'Sheen Phäih has forty goats.'
(So-Hartmann 2009: 218)

Locative frame

- (418) Ah püi = e sun khuui-k'um = a **ve** = kti = e
POSS:3S friend = PL DEM cave-inside = LOC be.at = NON.FUT = PL
'His friends are in the cave.'
(So-Hartmann 2009: 218)

'live'

- (419) Ah kkhyu: vai phi am ve kti = a ah pät sa: **ve-ei** = kti.
POSS:3S wife SUBJ also NEG exist NON.FUT = CF S.AGR:3S self small live-AO = NON.FUT
'Having nobody to take as a wife, he lived all by himself.'
(So-Hartmann 2009: 343)

Copula

(420) Ahin ta vok-ee:k-tui: ni.
DEM.PRO:this FOC pig-shit-water COP

‘This is water [polluted by] pig shit.’

(So-Hartmann 2009: 142)

UNCLASSIFIED SINO-TIBETAN

68. Caijia 蔡家话 (Hezhang, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

(421) mɔ²¹ ku⁵⁵ yã²¹ u²¹ts^ho²¹ fɛ⁵¹ sɿ⁵⁵.
that moment there.be people family CONT

‘There once was a family.’

(*The corn and the grass* text, Shanshan Lü)

Possessive frame

(422) je³³ yã²¹ la²¹ ɔ⁵⁵ ji³³ pie²¹.
3SG have big house one CLF

‘He has a big house.’

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü)

Locative frame

- (423) ηo^{33} **tu^{21}** ɔ^{55} zi^{21} .
1SG be.at house inside
'I'm at home.'

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü)

'live' & locative preposition

- (424) ηo^{33} **tu^{21}** ti^{21} ty^{33} **tu^{21}** .
1SG at hill upside live
'I live on the hill.'

(*Field Notes*, Shanshan Lü)

69. Jianchuan Bai 剑川白语 (Jianchuan, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

- (425) $\text{t}\check{\text{c}}\text{h}\tilde{\text{e}}^{55}$ xu^{31} **tsu^{33}** khe^{44} .
room inside there.be guest
'There are guests in the room.'

(Xu and Zhao 1984: 39)

Possessive frame

- (426) a³¹no³⁵ mo³³ va⁴² **tsu³³** tɕi³¹ta⁵⁵ pɛ⁴².
NAME mother PROP have scissor CLF
'Ano's mother has a pair of scissors.'

(Xu and Zhao 1984: 23)

Locative frame

- (427) ŋu⁵⁵ ke³³mo³³ **tsu³³** xa³¹tɥ̃⁵⁵ nɛ⁵⁵?
1SG.POSS mother-in-law be.at home Q
'Is my mother-in-law at home?'

(Xu and Zhao 1984: 88)

Copula

- (428) ŋo³¹ **tsu³³** nu⁵⁵ ta⁵⁵.
1SG COP 2SG.POSS elder sister
'I'm your elder sister.'

(Xu and Zhao 1984: 40)

70-72. Lanping Bai 兰坪白语, Shitou Bai 石头白语, and Yunlong Bai 云龙白语 (Yunnan, China)

	Existential & possessive	Locative	Copula
Lanping Bai	zɿ ³³	zɿ ³³	zɿ ³³
Shitou Bai	ndzɿ ³³	ndzɿ ³³	ndzɿ ³³
Yunlong Bai	dzu ³³	dzu ³³	dzu ³³

(Li 2014: 75)

HMONG-MIEN

73. Younuo 优诺语 (Longsheng, Guangxi AR. China)

Existential frame

(429) koŋ¹³ tu³⁵ mo¹³ ze²² tiu¹³ le⁵³ haŋ²¹.

mountain foot there.be one CLF small river

‘There’s a small river at the foot of the mountain.’

(Mao and Li 2007: 86)

Possessive frame

(430) vɔ²² mɔ¹³ zɛ²² lən³⁵ tshun³⁵ o³³.
1sg have one CLF red clothes

‘I have an item of red clothes.’

(Mao and Li 2007: 124)

Locative frame

(431) zɑ¹³çi²² naŋ²² nɑŋ³³ pje²² ŋ¹³ thi³¹ tən³⁵ naŋ²² tɔ¹³.
if 3SG be.at home 2SG then invite 3SG come

‘If he’s at home, invite him to come.’

(Mao and Li 2007: 95)

Locative preposition

(432) vɔ²² nɑŋ³³ kə³³lin¹³ ŋɔ³⁵kəŋ³³.
1SG at field work

‘I work in the field.’

(Mao and Li 2007: 97)

‘live’

(433) naŋ²²-nɔ¹³ ne²²nɔ³³ **naŋ**³³ te³³ no²².
3-PL today live here
'They will live here today.'
(Mao and Li 2007: 67)

Copula

(434) no²² **ɕi**²¹ naŋ²² kə³¹.
this COP 3SG POSS
'This is his.'
(Mao and Li 2007: 82)

74. White Hmong (Laos)

Existential frame

(435) thaum ub **muaj** [ib tug tsov]_s
time yonder exist one CLF tiger
'Once upon a time, there was a tiger.'
(Jarkey 2015: 44)

Possessive frame

(436) kuv_A **muaj** [ob tug me-nyuam]_o
1SG have two CLF children
'I have two children.'
(Jarkey 2015: 49)

'grasp'

(437) ces txawm yuav **muab** niag cuam noj nyoos ntag no
CONJ then IRR take great gibbon eat be.raw IP IP
'...and then (he) was going to take that big ol' gibbon (and) eat (it) raw.'
(Jarkey 2015: 269)

Locative frame

(438) nkawd **nyob** nram hav-dej
3DU be.at down valley-water
'They are down in the river valley.'
(Jarkey 2015: 51)

Locative preposition

(439) cov me-nyuam ua.si (**nyob**) hauv luv vaj

CLF.PL child play at inside CLF garden

‘The children are playing in the garden.’

(Jarkey 2015: 203)

‘live’

(440) thaum kuv los **nyob** lub teb.chaws no
time 1SG come live CLF country this

‘...the time I came to live in this country.’

(Jarkey 2015: 203)

Coplula

(441) plas **yog** noog
owl COP bird

‘Owls are birds.’

(Jarkey 2015: 45)

75. Weining Hmong 威宁苗语 (Weining, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame & locative preposition

(442) **no**⁵⁵ vfai³¹ lai⁵⁵ gfau³¹ tau⁵⁵ **mfa**³⁵ i⁵⁵ la³⁵ ce⁵⁵.

at there CLF back mountain have one CLF lake

‘There’s a lake behind the mountain.’

(Wang and Wang 1982: 28)

Possessive frame

(443) “ku⁵⁵ hi³³ mfi³⁵ nau⁵⁵ lo³¹, [...]”

1SG NEG have wife PRT

‘I don’t have a wife.’

(Wang 1986: 73)

Locative frame

(444) ku⁵⁵ ntey⁵⁵ no⁵⁵ q^ho⁵⁵ dy^{31-53?}

1SG book be.at place which

‘Where is my book?’

(Wang and Wang 1982: 34)

‘live’

(445) nfi¹¹ no⁵⁵ lai⁵⁵ ngfi³⁵ a³¹dzi³¹.

3SG dwell CLF house upside

‘He lives in the house that is above.’

(Wang and Wang 1982: 26)

Copula

(446) lai⁵⁵ pi⁵⁵ŋtau⁵⁵ ku¹¹ ku⁵⁵ bie⁵³.

CLF middle COP 1SG POSS

‘The one in middle is mine.’

(Wang and Wang 1982: 30)

76. Yanghao Hmong 养蒿苗语 (Yanghao, Guizhou, China)

naŋ³³

Existential frame

(447) haŋ³⁵noŋ³⁵ naŋ³³ i³³ pen⁵⁵ tu³⁵.

here there.be one CLF book

‘There’s a book here.’

(Wang 1985: 72)

Possessive frame

(448) naŋ⁵⁵ sei⁵⁵ naŋ³³, naŋ¹¹ sei⁵⁵ naŋ³³.

eat also have wear also have
'(We) have food, and (we) also have clothes.'
(Wang 1985: 76)

Locative frame

(449) le³³ ti⁴⁴ **ŋaŋ**³³ haŋ³⁵noŋ³⁵.
CLF bowl be.at here
'The bowl is here.'
(Wang 1985: 56)

'sit, dwell'

(450) **ŋaŋ**³³ 'sit', 'dwell'
(Wang 1985: 183, 184)

me⁵³

Existential frame

(451) a⁵⁵ **me**⁵⁵ ə³³ zə¹¹.
NEG there.be water PRT
'There's no more water.'

(Wang 1985: 69)

- (452) vi¹¹ tse³⁵ **me**⁵⁵ tsa³³ le⁵⁵ ne⁵⁵.
1SG home there.be five CLF people
'There're five people in our family.'

(Wang 1985: 88)

Possessive frame

- (453) vi¹¹ **me**⁵⁵ i³³ le³³ shaŋ⁴⁴.
1SG have one CLF umbrella
'I have an umbrella.'

(Wang 1985: 80)

Copula

- (454) le³³ noŋ³⁵ **ti**¹³ le³³ qei⁵⁵ ɕi³⁵? Copula
CLF this COP CLF what
'What's this?'

(Wang 1985: 56)

77. Aizhai Xong 矮寨苗语 (Aizhai, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(455) te⁵³ u⁵³ me³¹ ma³¹-ljəŋ³¹ mzu⁴⁴.

small river there.be NMLZ-big fish

‘There’s big fish in the river.’

(Yu 2010: 82)

Possessive frame

(456) we⁴⁴ me³¹ zəŋ²²?

1SG have strength

‘I have strength.’

(Yu 2010: 82)

Locative frame

(457) xə⁵³be⁴⁴ ŋi⁵³ ləŋ³⁵ tso⁵³.

ladle be.at upside oven

‘The ladle is on the oven.’

(Yu 2010: 39)

Locative preposition

(458) ta⁵³ci⁵³ naŋ⁴⁴ nu²² kə⁵³lə⁵³ tɕɛ³⁵ ɲi⁵³ po³¹tsha³⁵.

soft-shelled.turtle POSS egg still hide at sand

‘The eggs of soft-shelled turtle are still hidden in the sand.’

(Yu 2010: 37)

Copula

(459) du³⁵ kje⁴⁴tsɿ⁴⁴ ɲi²² ne³¹pzɯ⁴⁴ naŋ⁴⁴.

tree orange COP other POSS

‘The orange tree is someone else’s.’

(Yu 2010: 37)

78. Fenghuang Xong 凤凰苗语 (Fenghuang, Hunan, China)

Existential frame

(460) Bid-gheul laot-gheul mex aod-ngonl daob-mel.

FRT-mountain top-place₂ exist one-CLF:animate AN-horse

‘There’s a horse on the mountain top.’

(Sposato 2017: 391)

Possessive frame

- (461) Aod-dieud dox Sank.ux.baob naond qik.zib **mex** ngonl deb-deb.
one-CLF:time₂ that PN ASSOC wife have CLF:animate child-RED
'At that time, San U Bao's wife had a child.'
(Sposato 2017: 230)

Locative frame

- (462) Ob-ras **ninb** dof?
NOM-comb at which
'Where is the comb?'
(Sposato 2017: 565)

Locative preposition

- (463) Wel **ninb** bioud dieud hlit
1SG at home boil.rice cooked.rice
'I'll boil the rice here at home.'
(Sposato 2017: 565)

Copula

- (464) [[Jont ninb ghaob-deut-ndaut] naond] aod-meinl dox doub **nins** xob.zhaonx.
 [[sit at NOM-foot-tree] ASSOC] one-CLF:person that then₁ COP principal
 ‘That person sitting under the tree is (our school’s) principal.’
 (Sposato 2017: 357)

79. Songtao Xong 松桃苗语 (Songtao, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

- (465) tɕaŋ⁴² ntu⁵⁴li⁴⁴ tu³⁵ **me**³¹ pi⁴⁴li⁴⁴ ca⁵⁴.
 plant plum.tree then there.be plum eat
 ‘If we plant plum trees, there will be plums to eat.’
 (Luo 2005: 159)

Possessive frame

- (466) wu⁴⁴ **me**³¹ u³⁵ le³⁵ te^{35.31}te³⁵.
 3SG have two CLF child
 ‘He has two children.’
 (Luo 2005: 212)

Locative frame

(467) ɕaŋ⁴⁴tseŋ³⁵hu⁵⁴ tu³⁵ ɲi³⁵ ka²²a⁴⁴.
township.government just be.at there
'The township government is just over there.'
(Luo 2005: 77)

Locative preposition

(468) muŋ³⁵ tɕuŋ⁵⁴ ɲi³⁵ qɔ⁵⁴tɕi³⁵?
2SG live (< 'sit') at where
'Where do you live?'
(Luo 2005: 159)

Copula

(469) muŋ³⁵ ɲi⁴² qɣ³⁵ɕuŋ³⁵.
2SG COP Xong
'You are a Xong.'
(Luo 2005: 120)

80. Jiongnai 炯奈语 (Jinxiu, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

(470) mpha³⁵ mi⁴⁴ mɔ³³ laŋ⁴⁴ ŋkjɔŋ⁵³ pɔ⁴³.
side that there.be CLF mountain big
'There's a big mountain on that side.'
(Mao and Li 2002: 57)

Possessive frame

(471) naŋ³¹ mɔ³³ tʃen⁴⁴ nten⁵³ ne⁴⁴.
3SG have CLF knife small
'He has a small knife.'
(Mao and Li 2002: 57)

Locative frame

(472) va³¹ naŋ⁴⁴ ne⁵³.
1SG be.at here
'I'm here.'
(Mao and Li 2002 :44)

Locative preposition

(473) maŋ³³ naŋ⁴⁴ pja⁵³ tʃe³⁵ ʃa³⁵?

2SG at house do what

‘What are you doing at home?’

(Mao and Li 2002: 46)

‘sit, dwell’

(474) **naŋ**⁴⁴ ‘sit, dwell, be at’

(Mao and Li 2002: 284)

Copula

(475) laŋ⁴⁴ ne⁵³ **jei**²² va³¹ va⁵³.

CLF this COP 1SG wife

‘This is my wife.’

(Mao and Li 2002: 45)

81. Baheng 巴哼语 (Rongshui, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

(476) ta⁴⁴ ɲtɕe⁵³ **mfi**³¹ pja³⁵ nfi³¹ he³⁵he³⁵.

that.YON side there.be five CLF sheep

‘There’re five sheep over there.’

(Mao and Li 1997: 38)

Possessive frame

(477) a⁵⁵ʃfiu³¹! je³¹ qε⁵³ tɕfi³³ vfi³¹ tfi³³ a³¹ mfi³³ vfi³¹.
whoops one CLF money 1SG even NEG have PFV
'Whoops! I don't even have one yuan!'

(Mao and Li 1997: 67)

Locative frame

(478) nfiu³¹ n̄ō³⁵ pjo³¹ pɣ³³.
3SG be located home Q
'Is he at home? (with presumption that he is at home)'

(Mao and Li 1997: 66)

Locative preposition

(479) nfiu³¹mɰ⁵⁵ n̄ō³⁵ a⁴⁴pjo³¹ nfi³³ i⁵³.
3PL at house eat dinner
'They have dinner at home.'

(Mao and Li 1997: 61)

‘sit’

(480) vfĩ³¹ n̥õ³⁵ ŋ³¹na³⁵.

1SG sit here

‘I’ll sit here.’

(Mao and Li 1997: 74)

‘live’

(481) nfiu³¹ n̥õ³⁵ a⁴⁴pjo³¹ s̃⁵⁵ŋi⁵⁵.

3SG live house too small

‘The house he lives in is too small.’

(Mao and Li 1997: 54)

Copula

(482) vfĩ³¹ (ɕi⁵³) pa³¹ŋŋ³⁵.

1SG COP Baheng

‘I’m a Baheng.’

(Mao and Li 1997: 36)

82. Chiang Saen Iu Mien (Chiang Saen, Chiang Rai, Thailand)

Existential frame

- (483) dau³³kaʔ³¹ n̄wa²⁴ **ma:i⁵³** tɕen⁵⁵ jet³¹ kwan⁵³ juŋ⁵³.
field inside there.be DUR one flock sheep
'There is a flock of sheep in the field.'
(Saeliao 2012: 331)

Possessive frame

- (484) mei⁵³ **ma:i⁵³** tɕen⁵⁵ tɕem³³.
2SG have DUR gold
'You have gold.'
(Saeliao 2012: 331)

Locative frame

- (485) sjen³³lɔ⁵³ **jem³³** t^hai⁵⁵tei³¹ baʔ³¹doŋ²⁴ ua⁵⁵ puŋ³³.
Bangkok be.at Thailand middle that side
'Bangkok is in the middle part of Thailand.'
(Saeliao 2012: 228)

‘live’

(486) pjau⁵⁵kaɿ³¹ n̄wa²⁴ jem³³ tɕen⁵⁵ i³³ tɔi²⁴ mjen⁵³.
home inside live DUR two pair person

‘There are two couples living at home.’

(Saeliao 2012: 333)

Copula

(487) je³³ tshau⁵³ nin⁵³ sei³³ tsiŋ⁵³xai⁵⁵ mjen⁵³.
1SG and 3SG COP Chiangrai person

‘He and I are Chiangrai natives.’

(Saeliao 2012: 336)

83. Mae Chan Iu Mien (Mae Chan, Chiang Rai, Thailand)

Existential frame

(488) m̄[˧] ma:i[˧] n̄a:ŋ[˧] jan[˧]
neg there.be rice eat

‘There was no food to eat.’

Arisawa (2016: 456)

Possessive frame

- (489) maiŋ ma:iŋ koŋt tsəuŋ
neg have work do
'not have a job to do'
Arisawa (2016: 457)

Locative frame

- (490) ts^huŋt jemt t^hoŋŋ ka ɲuəŋ
unmilled.rice be.at bucket inside
'Unmilled rice is in the bucket.'
Arisawa (2016: 705)

'live'

- (491) uəŋtsanŋ ta:iŋ jemt uəŋ ciəŋ boŋt
DEM.time come live DEM upper.side mountain
'At that time (we) came to live there upper side of the mountain (in Laos).'

Copula

- (492) fuʔ.ɿciəʔ **pen** jəuʔ
 Fu Jiem COP younger.brother
 ‘Fu Jiem is (our) younger brother.’
 Arisawa (2016: 564)

84. Lakha 拉珈语 (Jinxiu, Guagxi AR, China)

Existential frame

- (493) ba:n³ ŋan² **mi**² in³ nam⁵ tam².
 village that there.be one CLF pond
 ‘There’s a pond in that village.’
 (Mao et al. 1982: 165)

Possessive frame

- (494) lak⁸ **mi**² in³ nam⁵ huə¹ ko:ŋ⁵.
 3SG have one CLF flower red
 ‘He has a red flower.’
 (Mao et al. 1982: 165)

Locative frame

- (495) tsi¹ at⁷ li².
1SG be.at here
'I'm here.'
(Mao et al. 1982: 141)

Locative preposition

- (496) nuŋ⁴jei⁴ at⁷ ou⁴ tsiẽ¹ pok⁸ŋo:m⁵.
child at inside river swim
'The children are swimming in the river.'
(Mao et al. 1982: 151)

Copula

- (497) lak⁸ tok⁷ pak⁷tsiŋ¹ ŋjun². Copula
3SG COP Beijing person
'He's from Beijing.'
(Mao et al. 1982: 166)

85. [Bunu](#) 布努语 (Hechi, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

- (498) ta²min⁸ɕan¹ nu³⁻³ moŋ² kwaŋ² ɲɕy⁶.
Damingshan DEM.YON there.be mineral resources many
'There're many mineral resources in Damingshan.'
(Mao et al. 1982: 87)

Possessive frame

- (499) kau² moŋ²⁻² mpau⁶ pon³ θɣ¹?
2SG have how many CLF book
'How many books do you have?'
(Mao et al. 1982: 114)

Locative frame

- (500) kau² tse³⁻³ ɲi¹ khi³⁻³tau⁶?
2SG home be.at where
'Where's your home?'
(Mao et al. 1982: 110)

Locative preposition

- (501) kau² ŋkoŋ⁵ mu² ɲi¹⁻¹ kau² he¹⁻¹kwaŋ².

2SG look 3PL at DEM.PROX mine

'Look! They're mining over there.'

(Mao et al. 1982: 87)

'live'

(502) **ji**¹ 'live'

(Mao et al. 1982: 215)

Copula

(503) nau³ (**ɕi**⁶) ɕoŋ².

this COP table

'This is a table.'

(Mao et al. 1982: 84)

(504) cuŋ (**tau**⁶) nu² kwɑŋ¹θai¹.

1SG COP person Guangxi

'I'm from Guangxi.'

(Mao et al. 1982: 85)

86. She 畬语 (Huidong, Guangdong, China)

Existential frame

(505) a¹fuŋ³ ma² pi¹ kɔ⁵ thaŋ⁴ ɔi⁶.
river there.be five six CLF duck

‘There’re five or six ducks in the river.’

(Mao and Meng 1986: 74)

Possessive frame

(506) muŋ² kɣ⁵ne² ma² pɣ⁴ naŋ¹ suŋ¹taŋ¹?
2SG HON have how.many CLF grandson

‘How many grandsons do you have?’

(Mao and Meng 1986: 45)

Locative frame

(507) vaŋ⁴ kɣ⁶ nja⁴ muŋ² kɣ⁶ va⁴.
1SG be.at here 2SG be.at there

‘I’m here; you’re there.’

(Mao and Meng 1986: 55)

Locative preposition

(508) nuŋ⁴ kɣ⁶ a¹fuŋ³ tsji³ tɔ⁵.
3SG at river wash foot
'He's washing his feet in the river.'
(Mao and Meng 1986: 55)

'give'

(509) vaŋ⁴ kɣ⁶ nuŋ⁴ i⁶ phuŋ⁶ tɔ³.
1SG give 3SG one CLF book
'I gave him a book.'
(Mao and Meng 1986: 75)

Copula

(510) ka⁶thɔ⁴ thɔŋ² niu² tshi⁴ pa¹ a¹kuŋ⁶ ŋjuŋ⁴.
backside CLF house COP 1PL uncle POSS
'The house in the back is my uncle's.'
(Mao and Meng 1986: 59)

KRA-DAI

87. Judu Gelao 居都佬语 (Liupanshui, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

- (511) Λ^{33} dzoŋ³³ l Λ^{31} dzaŋ³¹ aŋ³¹ tsɿ³³ phai³⁵ su³¹.
upside table have one CLF book
'There's a book on the table.'
(Kang 2009: 50)

Possessive frame

- (512) mi³⁵ aŋ³⁵⁻³¹ sa³⁵ la³⁵ lai³³ a³¹ ləu³¹ san³⁵.
3SG have CLF child at Judu_{PLACENAME}
'He has a child in Judu.'
(Kang 2009: 245)

Locative frame

- (513) tɕ^hi³¹ nzi³⁵ məu³¹ a³¹/qau³³ ko³⁵ thu³³.
shoe 2SG be.at foot bed
'Your shoes are under the bed.'
(Kang 2009: 244; Zhongde Kang pers. comm.)

Locative preposition

(514) vu³¹no³⁵ **qau³³** tu³⁵ lui³¹ ɲu³³ɲa³⁵ ə³¹phau³⁵.
bird at sky without order fly

‘The birds are flying about in the sky.’

(Kang 2009: 244)

‘sit’

(515) mi³⁵ a³¹ den³¹ ʌ^{31?}lan³¹ **qau³³** ʒi³¹khen³¹.
3SG at side rode sit rest

‘He sat by the roadside to have a rest.’

(Kang 2009: 50)

‘live’

(516) di³³to³¹ ta³¹ kan³¹ tsi³³ **qau³³** a³¹ tu³¹lu³⁵ pai³⁵ai³³ bu³⁵.
1PL three CLF all live at village opposite DEM.DIST

‘We three all live in that village that is in the opposite side.’

(Kang 2009: 175)

Copula

- (517) ɲe³⁵laŋ³³ tɕi³³tɕo³¹ ɲi³⁵ au³¹ ləu³¹san³⁵.
 place 2PL this COP Judu_{PLACENAME}
 ‘Here is Judu.’
 (Kang 2009: 246)

88. Xia’ao Zhuang (Xia’ao, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

- (518) pai³³na⁴² ra:m⁴² mi¹³ ti:u²³¹ ta³¹ deu⁴².
 front house there.be CLF river one
 ‘There’s a river in front of the house.’
 (Wei 2012: 202)

Possessive frame

- (519) te⁴² mi²³¹⁻¹³tu¹³ lə:k¹³ deu⁴² ju³³ nan³¹nin³¹.
 3SG have CLF child one in Nanning_{PLACENAME}
 ‘He has a child in Nanning.’
 (Wei 2012: 217)

Locative frame

- (520) hai¹³ mə:ŋ²³¹ ju³³ la⁴² bo:n³³.
 shoe 2SG be.at downside bed
 ‘Your shoes are under the bed.’
 (Wei 2012: 154)

Locative preposition

- (521) ɕiau⁴²waŋ³¹ ju³³ kə:n²³¹ tɕo:ŋ²³¹ hə:n³¹ro:ŋ²³¹ ju³³.
 Xiaowang at upside table stand CONT
 ‘Xiaowang is standing on the table.’
 (Wei 2012: 34)

‘live’

- (522) ku⁴² ju³³ toi³³na⁴² ra:n²³¹ te⁴².
 1SG live opposite.side home 3SG
 ‘I live across from his home.’
 (Wei 2012: 86)

Copula

- (523) kai³³ pit⁵⁵ru⁴² ni¹³ ɕɿ³¹ pu³¹rəw²³¹ ti³³.

CLF pen this COP which POSS

‘Whose pen is this?’

(Wei 2012: 221)

(524) po³¹ ku⁴² **siŋ**³³ na¹³ te⁴².

father 1SG COP uncle 3SG

‘My father is his uncle.’

(Wei 2012: 220)

89. Lao

Existential frame

(525) **mii2** cot2-maaj3 naj2 hùan2 khòòng3 laaw2.

there.is letter in house of 3SG.FA

‘There was a letter in his house.’

(Enfield 2007: 158)

Possessive frame

(526) khòj5 **mii2** pùm4 lèèw4.

1SG.P have book PRF

'I already have a book.'

(Enfield 2007: 245)

Locative frame

(527) man2 **juu1** toq2.

3.B be.at table

'It's on/at the table.'

(Enfield 2007: 392)

Locative preposition

(528) phen1 lùaj1 maj4 **juu1** vat1

3.P saw wood at temple

'He's sawing wood at the temple.'

(Enfield 2007: 187)

'live'

(529) man2 **juu1** viang2can3.

3.B live/be.at Vietnam

'He lives in Vietnam/He is in Vietnam.'

(Enfield 2007: 186)

Copula

- (530) khaw3 **pên3** nakø-hian2
3PL.B COP CT.AGT-student
'They were students.'
(Enfield 2007: 285)

90. Nùng (Bắc Giang, Vietnam)

Existential frame

- (531) **mi** càu áhn phả vahn
there.be nice cl. cover day
'There were nine suns.'
(Saul and Wilson 1980: 74)

Possessive frame

- (532) mưhñ **mi** slám cộn kíhm
he have three lump gold
'He has three lumps of gold.'

(Saul and Wilson 1980: 19)

Locative frame

(533) mư̄hng **du** hơ̄n mư̄hng tẹ̄o pehn hử̄ lam-đáng
you at house you again like what pregnant

‘If you were at home, how could you become pregnant?’

(Saul and Wilson 1980: 118)

Locative preposition

(534) vahn này áhn bộ **du** láchng hơ̄n dách lái
day this cl. well at back house deep very

‘Today the well at the back of the house is very deep.’

(Saul and Wilson 1980: 70)

‘live’

(535) slí cữhn **du** chòn hơ̄n nử̄hng
four person live together house one

‘Four persons live together in one house.’

(Saul and Wilson 1980: 55)

Copula

- (536) mʉhn **du** cʉhn sláy
he is person priest
'He's a sorcerer.'
(Saul and Wilson 1980: 72)

91. Hlai 黎语 (Hainan, China)

Existential frame & locative preposition

- (537) ka:u³ tshi¹hau², **tsau²** tsur³ hom¹ hwe:ŋ¹ lom³ ʔbe:ŋ¹ ʔom³ ʔo:k⁷, **ʔdu³** hwe:ŋ¹ hau²
long.time moment there.be one CLF pool also wide also deep at pool there

tsau² taŋ¹ khu¹ koŋ¹nam³.
there.be dragon and aquatic.animal
'Once a while, there was a water pool wide and deep. There was a dragon there and other aquatic animals.'
(Yuan 1994: 187)

Possessive frame

- (538) na¹ man³ŋo:ŋ² **tsau²** tsur³ tsu:n¹ ʔu:k⁷.

3SG only have one CLF child

‘He only has one child.’

(Yuan 1994: 99)

Locative frame

(539) pha³za¹ ?du³ ploŋ³.

father be.at home

‘Father is at home.’

(Yuan 1994: 66)

Copula

(540) na¹ man¹ gu:ŋ¹ hou.

3SG COP younger.brother 1SG

‘He’s my younger brother.’

(Yuan 1994: 51)

92. Ong Be (Lingao, Hainan, China)

Existential frame

(541) lai³ leŋ⁴hun² dok⁷ nam⁴ la³.

there.be person fall water PRT

‘There’s someone falling into the water.’

(Zhang and Ma 1983: 59)

Possessive frame

(542) **lai**³ sin²

have money

‘have money’

(Liu 2000: 78)

(543) be² nə⁴ hu² **lai**³ ki³ na³ lək⁸.

man that CLF have several CLF child

‘That man has several children.’

(Liang 1981: 270)

‘obtain’

(544) **lai**³ mɔŋ⁸ kɔn¹ mɔŋ⁸.

obtain CLF eat CLF

‘Get one, eat one.’ or ‘Eat whatever you can get.’

(Liang 1981: 271)

Locative frame

(545) vən²nɔi⁴ hau² **jɔu³** lan².
today 1SG be.at house

‘I’m at home today.’

(Liu 2000: 141)

Locative preposition

(546) **jɔu³** lan² hɪu³sik⁸
at home rest

‘rest at home’

(Liu 2000: 141)

Copula

(547) kə² ti⁴ ləu²na³?

3 COP who

‘Who’s he?’

(Zhang and Ma 1983: 54)

93. Thai

Existential frame

- (548) pòkkatì **mii** khon mâak.
usually there.be person many
'Usually there are a lot of people.'
(Smyth 2013: 104)

Possessive frame

- (549) **mii** lûuk kîi khon?
have child how.many CLF
'How many children do you have?'
(Smyth 2013: 167)

Locative frame

- (550) bâan **yùu** thîi nôon.
house be.at at there
'The house is over there.'
(Smyth 2013: 108)

'live'

(551) raw khəy **yùu** thîi kruŋthêp

1PL used.to live at Bangkok

'We used to live in Bangkok.'

(Smyth 2013: 70)

Copula

(552) kháw **pen** phâan

3 COP friend

'He is a friend.'

(Smyth 2013: 56)

94. Dai 傣语 (Dehong, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(553) mu⁴ni?⁸ ka:ŋ¹xuⁿ² bau⁵ **mi²** tɛn⁵.

today evening NEG there.be electricity

'There will be no electricity tonight.'

(Yu and Luo 1980: 33)

Possessive frame

- (554) kau⁶ mi² in²lən⁶.
1SG have a little
'I have a little.'
(Yu and Luo 1980: 44)

Locative frame

- (555) phau¹ kɔ³ jaŋ⁶ ju⁵.
who also NEG be.at
'No one is here.'
(Yu and Luo 1980: 63)

Locative preposition

- (556) xau¹tsau³ ju⁵ ti⁶han³ ɔm⁵ dət⁹.
3PL at there burn sunshine
'They are sun bathing over there.'
(Yu and Luo 1980: 63)

'live'

(557) **ju**⁵ 'live'

(Yu and Luo 1980: 125)

Copula

(558) to¹xa³ **pin**¹ pɔ⁶hai⁶mɛ⁶na².

1SG COP farmer

'I'm a farmer.'

(Yu and Luo 1980: 88)

95. Sui 水语 (Qiannan, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

(559) ɣa³⁵ na:i²⁴ **ʔnaŋ**¹¹ mom²⁴.

field this there.be fish

'There're fishes in the field.'

(Wei 2011: 219)

Possessive frame

(560) ai³¹ **ʔnaŋ**¹¹ le¹¹, me³¹ **ʔnaŋ**¹¹ ɕen³¹.

1SG have book NEG have money

'I have books, but don't have money.'

(Wei 2011: 220)

Locative frame

(561) pu³¹ nǝ³¹ ɲa:u²⁴ ɣa:n³¹ me³¹?

father 2SG be.at home NEG:Q

'Is your father at home?'

(Wei 2011: 286)

Locative preposition

(562) ai³¹ ha:ŋ⁵³ ɲa:u²⁴ kui¹¹tsau³³.

1SG be.born at Guizhou

'I was born in Guizhou.'

(Wei 2011: 290)

'live'

(563) man¹¹ ɲa:u²⁴ ɣa:n³¹ ma³⁵.

3SG live new home

‘He lives in the new house.’

(Wei 2011: 326)

Copula

(564) man¹¹ pu⁵³ vən⁵³

3SG father NAME

‘He’s Wen’s father.’

(Wei 2011: 247)

(565) man¹¹ **n³³dum** çen¹¹tsaŋ⁵⁵.

3SG COP county.magistrate

‘He is the county magistrate.’

(Wei 2011: 323)

(566) tak⁵⁵ za³⁵ **tju³¹** tsən¹¹tsaŋ⁵⁵ ljeu¹¹.

CLF that COP town.mayor PRT

‘That is the town mayor.’

(Wei 2011: 323)

- (567) van¹¹na:i²⁴ sɿ¹¹ ɕin³³ɦi¹¹u⁵⁵
today COP Friday
'Today is Friday.'
(Wei 2011: 323)

96. Maonan (Huanjiang, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

- (568) ja:u³ ja:n¹ me² sa:m¹ ?ai¹ zən¹ na⁴ k^ha:u³
inside house have three CL:person person eat wine
'In the house there are three people drinking wine.'
(Lu 2008: 211)

Possessive frame

- (569) man² me² ?dat⁸ ja:n¹ ?ni⁵ ?deu².
3SG have CL:hard:object house small one
'He owns a small house.'
(Lu 2008: 232)

Locative frame

(570) van¹na:i⁶ man² ɲa:u⁶ ja:n¹
today 3SG stay home
'Today he is at home.'
(Lu 2008: 264)

Locative preposition

(571) man² ɲa:u⁶ ?ju¹ pɔŋ³ non².
3SG at top bed sleep
'S/he slept on the bed.'
(Lu 2008: 175)

'live'

(572) ?dat⁸ ja:n¹ [() se¹ ɲa:u⁶] ka⁵ ?ni⁵ pa:i¹
CL:object house 2PL live that small go
'The house where they live is too small.'
(Lu 2008: 205)

Copula

(573) man² ɕi⁴/tsiŋ⁵ de² fie² ɕi⁴/tsiŋ⁵ la:k⁸.

3SG to.be father 1SG to.be child

'He is the father, I am the child.'

(Lu 2008: 265)

97. Mak (Cham) 锦话 (Qiannan, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame & 'live'

(574) **naŋ**¹ tə sɿ³ deu¹ **ŋa:u**⁶ a:u⁶ si⁵.

there.be lion one live inside that

'There's a lion living inside.'

(Yang 2000: 284)

Possessive frame

(575) ŋ² ai³la:u⁴ **naŋ**¹ tɿ³ lak⁸ ɭa:n¹ la⁴?

2SG HON have how.many CLF grandson PRT

'How many grandsons do you have?'

(Yang 2000: 128)

Locative frame

(576) to²ma¹ tjat⁸ **ŋa:u**⁶ a:u³ ja:n¹.

CLF dog be.at inside house

'The dog is at home.'

(Yang 2000: 112)

Locative preposition

(577) ma³ **na:u⁶** tə³fin¹ zu⁴ ma¹.
mother at vegetable.garden plant vegetable

'My mom is planting vegetable in the garden.'

(Yang 2000: 112)

Copula

(578) man¹ **cin¹/s¹** ai¹ ŋau¹?
3SG COP CLF who

'Who is he?'

(Yang 2000: 101)

98. Bouyei 布依语 (Longli, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

(579) tin¹ po¹ pa:i⁶la³ **li⁴** tɕuaŋ⁶ ka:m³ diau¹.

hill foot under there.be cave cave one

‘There’s a cave at the foot of the hill.’

(Yu 1980: 53)

Possessive frame

(580) ti¹ li⁴ sa:m¹ va:ʔ⁸ tɕai¹.

3SG have three CLF plough

‘He has three ploughs.’

(Yu 1980: 32)

Locative frame

(581) vaʔ⁷ kuə⁸ ʔju⁵ kʉn²kʉn² te¹.

CLF hoe be.at top that

‘The hoe is on the top.’

(Mo 2017: 59)

(582) ʔju⁵ ‘be at’

(Yu 1980: 99)

Locative preposition

- (583) ti¹ ʔju⁵ zan⁵ta⁶ sa[?]7 pu⁶.
3SG at riverside wash clothes
'She's washing clothes at the riverside.'
(Yu 1980: 35)

'live'

- (584) ku¹ ka:[?]5 ʔju⁵.
1SG alone live
'I live alone.'
(Yu 1980: 37)

Copula

- (585) ti¹ si¹ lu[?]8su¹.
3SG COP student
'He's a student.'
(Yu 1980: 47)

99. Kam 侗语 (Qiandongnan, Guizhou, China)

Existential frame

(586) ma:ŋ⁵ ɕe^{1/} ja:n² **me²** sa:m^{1/} oŋ¹ məi⁴.
side left house there.be three CLF tree

‘There’re three trees on the left of the house.’

(Liang 1980: 37)

Possessive frame

(587) ma:u⁵ **me²** i¹ ʈa:i⁴ ja² noŋ⁴.
3SG have one elder.brother two younger.brother

‘He has one elder brother and two younger brothers.’

(Liang 1980: 83)

Locative frame

(588) ma:u⁶ **ŋa:u⁶** wu¹wu¹ ʈa⁵.
3SG be.at top that

‘He’s at the top.’

(Liang 1980: 37)

Locative preposition

(589) ma:u⁶ sui⁵ ɲa:u⁶ te³ məi⁴ ʈa⁵.
3SG sit at bottom tree that
'He's sitting under that tree.'
(Liang 1980: 56)

'live'

(590) ma:u⁶ ɲa:u⁶ ʈa⁵ li³ mjeŋ² ɲin² la⁴.
3SG live that obtain several year PFV
'He's been living there for several years.'
(Liang 1980: 41)

Copula

(591) ma:u⁶ ʈa:ŋ³ ti¹tʂa:ŋ⁴.
3SG COP teamleader
'He's the team leader.'
(Liang 1980: 50)

(592) khwa:i¹/tʂi¹ ʈiŋ⁵ ja:u².
bookkeeper COP 1SG

'I'm the bookkeeper.'

(Liang 1980: 50)

100. Mulao 仫佬语 (Luocheng, Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

(593) hwi⁵ mɛ² mu⁶ çən¹.
that there.be CLF person

'There's a person over there.'

(Yin 2012: 272)

Possessive frame

(594) əi² mɛ² ɣa² la:k⁸.
1SG have two child

'I have two children.'

(Yin 2012: 273)

Locative frame

(595) kə⁶pon¹ ɲa:u⁶ wu¹ tsja¹.
just.now be.at upside car

‘(I) was in the car.’

(Yin 2012: 379)

Locative preposition

(596) mɔ̃⁶ mɛ² nə³ twa⁶ hɣə:n² ɲa:u⁶ ləu¹tsəu¹.

3SG have one CLF house at Liuzhou

‘He has a house in Liuzhou.’

(Yin 2012: 274)

‘live’

(597) ni¹ mɔ̃⁶ ɲa:u⁶ hɣə:n² tshəi⁴.

mother 3SG live/be.at home Cui_{NAME}

‘His mother lives/is at Cui’s.’

(Yin 2012: 109)

Copula

(598) pu¹ mɔ̃⁶ si⁶ thjen⁵sej¹.

father 3SG COP teacher

‘His father is a teacher.’

(Yin 2012: 269)

101. E 五色话 (Rongshui Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame

(599) ma:i³ kyn² **mi**² sa:m¹ tɕɔ²ŋɔk⁷.
tree upside there.be three CLF bird

‘There are three birds in the tree.’

(Wei and Wei 2011: 184)

Possessive frame

(600) ku¹ **mi**² jet⁷ mje⁵ te⁶ sɔŋ¹ mje⁵ mɔi⁶.
1SG have one CLF younger.brother two CLF younger.sister

‘I have one younger brother and two younger sisters.’

(Wei and Wei 2011: 181)

Locative frame

(601) ŋ² kɔ³ ɕy¹ **u**⁵ tai:i² kyn².
2SG POSS book be.at table upside

‘Your book is on the table.’

(Wei and Wei 2011: 182)

Locative preposition

- (602) ku¹ u⁵ phja¹ kyn² ?ηak⁷ ?mun¹.
1SG at hill upside chop wood
'I cut wood on the hill.'

(Wei and Wei 2011: 189)

- (603) u⁵ 'live' 'be at'

(Wei and Wei 2011: 376)

Copula

- (604) mɔ⁶ ɕi⁶ thit⁷tsəŋ⁶.
3SG COP blacksmith
'He is a blacksmith.'

(Wei and Wei 2011: 184)

102. [Wuming Zhuang \(Wuming, Guangxi AR, China\)](#)

Existential frame

(605) **mi**² da⁷ yin¹ he¹.
 there.be CLF stone one
 ‘There is a stone.’
 (Zhang et al. 1999: 405)

Possessive frame

(606) kau¹ bau³ **mi**² θak⁷ ti¹.
 1SG NEG have any little
 ‘I have nothing at all.’
 (Zhang et al. 1999: 401)

Locative frame

(607) “... pan⁵ ki³ fuk⁷lok⁸ **ʔjau**⁵ laŋ¹ pau⁴lau¹ ta⁶?” ... “**ʔjau**⁵ laŋ¹ koŋ¹ta¹ nai⁴!”
 so some luck be.at at who PRT be.at at grandpa here
 ‘“Which person is so much luck on?”... “(It’s) on grandpa.”’
 (Zhang et al. 1999: 881)

‘live’

(608) te¹ **ʔjau**⁵ kwa:ŋ³θi⁶ wu³miŋ².

3SG live Guangxi Wuming

‘He lives in Guangxi Wuming.’

(Zhang et al. 1999: 425)

Copula

(609) pau⁴ θa:ŋ¹ **tuuk**⁸ nuəŋ⁴ kau¹.

size tall COP younger.brother 1SG

‘The tall one is my brother.’

(Zhang et al. 1999: 404)

AUSTRO-ASIATIC

103. Vietnamese

Existential frame

(610) **Có** mấy người trong nhà.

there.be several person in house

‘There are several persons in the house.’

(Phan 2010: 119)

Possessive frame

- (611) Tràng **có** vợ.
name have wife
'Tràng has wife.'
(Phan 2010: 123)

Locative frame

- (612) Nhà chị binh **ở** gần đường.
home wife soldier be.at vicinity road
'The soldier's wife's home is near the road.'
(Phan 2010: 121)

Locative preposition

- (613) Nguyệt đang nấp **ở** mé ngoài.
name just hide at outside
'Nguyệt is hiding outside.'
(Phan 2010: 139)

'live'

- (614) Em ở đây được 2 năm.
 1SG live here PFV two year
 ‘I have lived here for two years.’
 (Phan 2010: 136)

Copula

- (615) Cô hằng là giáo viên văn của tôi.
 teacher name COP teacher literature POSS 1SG
 ‘Hằng is my language teacher.’
 (Phan 2010: 120)

104. Jing 京语 (Vietnamese in Guangxi AR, China)

Existential frame and locative preposition

- (616) vi² ə³ ɲa² kɔ⁵ viək⁸, mə² ŋɔ⁶ di¹ tsəm⁶.
 because at home there.be thing so 1SG go late
 ‘Because there was something at home, I was late.’
 (Ouyang et al. 1984: 119)

- (617) juəŋ⁶ ten¹ nui⁵ khon¹ kɔ⁵ nuək⁷.

field upside hill NEG there.be water

‘There’s no water on the hill.’

(Ouyang et al. 1984: 111)

Possessive frame

(618) ηwəi²ηwəi² kuŋ³ kɔ⁵ koŋ¹ la:m².

everyone all have work do

‘Everyone has work to do.’

(Ouyang et al. 1984: 61)

Locative frame

(619) nɔ⁵ khoŋ¹ ə³ nə², thi² ə³ ηwa:i² juəŋ⁶.

3SG NEG be.at home then be.at outside field

‘If he’s not at home, he’s in the field then.’

(Ouyang et al. 1984: 117)

(620) do:i¹ hai:i² kuə³ mai² ə³ juəi⁵ tsən¹ juəŋ².

CLF shoe POSS 2SG be.at downside foot bed

‘Your shoes are under the bed.’

(Ouyang et al. 1984: 112)

Copula

- (621) tɛ³kən¹ nai² **la²** tot⁷ hək⁸tɔ².
child this COP good student
'This child is a good student.'

(Ouyang et al. 1984: 123)

105. Khmer (Cambodia)

Existential frame

- (622) knong sa'mot **mian** robawh robaw: miah pec kaev kaw:ng pitu:so:rkan craeun nah.
in sea have things gold jewel glass jewel treasure much very
'On the bottom of the sea there are lots of gold, jewels, treasures.'

(Haiman 2011: 208)

- (623) **mian** teuk, **mian** trej.
exist water exist fish
'If there's water, there's fish.'

(Haiman 2011: 315)

Possessive frame

- (624) preah awng **mian** preah riac botra: tae 5 awng ponno:h.
HON CL have hon king son only 5 CL that.many
'The king had only five sons.'
(Haiman 2011: 322)

- (625) ko:n **mian** pdej haeuj nevtae viaj pradav do:c ko:n kmee:ng.
child have husband and stillonly beat lecture like small youngster
'The daughter had a husband and (the mother) still beat and harangued her as if she were a small child.'
(Haiman 2011: 220)

Locative frame

- (626) camnaek puak tmej dael **nev** phu:m Tnawl
as.for group new who be.at village T.
'as for the new people who remained in the village of T.'
(Haiman 2011: 165)

- (627) cru:k **nev** kraom pteach.

pig be.at beneath house

‘The pig is under the house.’

(Haiman 2011: 212)

‘live, stay’

(628) aeng **nev** kawt na:

you stay dormitory which

‘Which building (monks’ dormitory) are you in?’

(Haiman 2011: 213)

(629) via **nev** cwt voat vi’hia Tanteum.

3 stay close temple pagada T.

‘They live close to the temple of T.’

(Haiman 2011: 213)

Copula

(630) cru:k **cia** neak tohtiaj.

pig COP person prophesy

‘The pig is a prophet.’

(Haiman 2011: 212)

- (631) aopuk mda:j A. **cia** neak camka:
father mother A. be person garden
'A.'s parents were (non-rice crop) farmers.'

(Haiman 2011: 212)

106. **Khmu** 克木语 (Xishuangbanna, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

- (632) bia? tm'pɣr **?ah** ŋɔ? tɕɛt tɕa? pm'sum.
crop turtledove there.be cereal seven type seed
'There're seven types of cereal seeds in the turtledove's crop.'

(Chen 2002: 318)

Possessive frame

- (633) ?o? **?ah** tep sam phum.
1SG have clothes three CLF
'I have three items of clothes.'

(Chen 2002: 167)

Locative frame

- (634) tɕn'tlɤŋjɔŋ sɛh mɤ? ?ai me **jiat** ɲi?.
horn father fall where Ai_{NAME} 2SG be.at there
'Ai, you'll be there where father's horn falls.'

(Chen 2002: 317)

Locative preposition

- (635) gu **jiat** khuimiŋ kɔŋtɕɔ?
3SG at Kunming work
'He works in Kunming.'

(Chen 2002: 176)

Copula

- (636) gi **mɤh** dɛn hɛm.
this COP bed younger.brother
'This is my younger brother's bed.'

(Chen 2002: 152)

107. Kemie 克蔑语 (Xishuangbanna, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

- (637) tu³⁵ nə̌ʔ⁵³ pǎʔ⁵³ nəŋ³¹ ma¹³ nəŋ³¹.
door house there.be hill one CLF
'There's a hill in front of the house.'

(Chen 2005: 78)

Possessive frame

- (638) ɣn³⁵ pǎʔ⁵³ suai³⁵ mun³⁵ ma³¹ tɕah³¹.
3SG have necklace silver one CLF
'She has a silver necklace.'

(Chen 2005: 77)

Locative frame/'live'

- (639) ɔʔ⁵³ ot³³ nə̌ʔ⁵³ meʔ⁵³.
1SG live/be.at house 2SG
'I live in yours/I'm at yours.'

(Chen 2005: 130, 217)

Serial verb construction with the first verb as ‘be at’

(640) ɣn³⁵ ot³³ kɣʔ⁵⁵ nǎʔ⁵³ gɛ³⁵ khiŋ⁵⁵.

3SG be.at at house comb head

‘He is at home combing his hair.’

(Chen 2005: 79)

Locative preposition

(641) meʔ⁵³ i³³ vek³³ ot³³ khɣʔ⁵³ ma¹³ʔ

2SG do thing at where

‘Where do you work?’

(Chen 2005: 83)

‘live’

(642) kɛʔ⁵³ ɔi³¹ i⁵³ ot³¹ kɣʔ⁵³ ɛ³⁵ him³⁵.

3PL three person live at that village

‘They three live in that village.’

(Chen 2005: 81)

Copula

(643) ɣn³⁵ kɣʔ⁵³ mɔ³¹ja³¹.

3SG COP doctor

‘He’s a doctor.’

(Chen 2005: 100)

108. Wa 佤语 (Lincang, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(644) sɿ bu:m pra:k ʔin kɔi ʔoʔ ra paŋ.

garden side this there.be bamboo two clump

‘There’re two clumps of bamboo beside the garden.’

(Zhou and Yan 1984: 49)

Possessive frame

(645) ʔɣʔ kɔi ma:n ɣa:n.

1SG have cloth so.wide

‘I have a piece of cloth that is so wide.’

(Zhou and Yan 1984: 57)

Locative frame

(646) ʔin məh lai tɕie məiʔ, (lai) tɕie ʔɿʔ ʔot piaŋ phuŋ.
this COP book poss 2SG book poss 1SG be.at upside table

‘This is your book, mine is on the table.’

(Zhou and Yan 1984: 70)

‘live’

(647) pə rauk ʔot kəh gəŋ, siəm ʔot dəuʔ toŋ.
Wa.people live at mountain Dai.people live in flat.area

‘Wa people live in the mountains; Dai people live on the plains.’

(Huang and Wang 1994: 36)

Copula

(648) nəh məh pui pɿʔ tɕiŋ.
3SG COP person Beijing

‘He’s Pekinese.’

(Zhou and Yan 1984: 36)

109. Bumang 布芒语 (Honghe, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(649) i⁵¹ **hop**²¹ pɛ⁵⁵ ti²⁴kɔi⁵⁵ lɛ²⁴ u⁵⁵.
this there.be fruit banana many very

‘There’re many bananas here.’

(Dao 2007: 70)

Possessive frame

(650) ɲa⁵⁵ pia⁵⁵ **hɔp**²¹ ku⁵⁵a⁵⁵ lǎm⁵¹ tseu⁵⁵ o²¹?
family 2PL have how.many CLF rubber.plant PRT

‘How many rubber plants does your family have?’

(Dao 2007: 92)

(651) kuam⁵¹vǎu²¹ ɲa⁵⁵ pa²⁴ jau⁵¹, kǎu⁵¹ **hop**²¹ he²⁴ tǎu²¹.
although 3SG height tall but have strength NEG

‘He is tall, but he doesn’t has strength.’

(Dao 2007: 151)

Locative frame

(652) pia⁵⁵ **ɲɔ**²⁴ ban¹² au⁵¹?

2PL live/be.at village which

‘Which village are you in/Which village do you live?’

(Dao 2007: 154, 244)

Locative preposition

(653) kən⁵⁵dit²⁴ nɔ²⁴ kən⁵⁵khuaŋ²⁴ te²⁴kua²⁴.

child at garden play

‘The children are playing in the garden.’

(Dao 2007: 64)

‘live’

(654) da⁵⁵ te²⁴ ka³³li²⁴ kǎu⁵¹ nɔ²⁴ ləi²⁴ bɔp²⁴ mɛ²⁴.

1SG from young then live with maternal grandmother

‘I have lived with my maternal grandmother since I was young.’

(Dao 2007: 114)

Copula

(655) da⁵⁵ pen⁵⁵ sɔ²¹sən⁵⁵.

1SG COP student

'I'm a student.'

(Dao 2007: 72)

110. Yunqian Palaung 允欠德昂语 (Luxi, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(656) la? plɛŋ ?ɣ **mɣh** pla:ŋ kiar ?ap vaŋ bli?.

upside sky NEG there.be moon dark

'There's no moon in the sky and it's dark.'

(Chen et al. 1986: 61)

Possessive frame

(657) **mɣh** so, tɕhɣ? ban dzɣih gru.

have money only obtain buy thing

'One can buy things only if one has money.'

(Chen et al. 1986: 97)

Locative frame

(658) giaŋ ?o **gɔi** la? rau veŋ khɛm.

home 1SG be.at village Yunqian_{NAME}

‘My home is in Yunqian village.’

(Chen et al. 1986: 58)

(659) ʔɛn mɔi **gɔi** laʔ ʔa:i, ʔɛn di gɔi laʔ ban.
POSS 2SG be.at front POSS 3SG be.at back

‘Yours are in the front, his are at the back.’

(Chen et al. 1986: 68)

Locative preposition

(660) di **gɔ:i** laʔ plɔ:ŋ toi ka.
3SG at inside river catch fish

‘He’s catching fish in the river.’

(Chen et al. 1986: 63)

‘live’

(661) ʔo **gɔi** gian mɔi.
1SG live home 2SG

‘I live at yours.’

(Chen et al. 1986: 90)

Copula

- (662) kiap tin mɔi **muh** kiap tin mai.
shoe 2SG COP shoe new
'Your shoes are new shoes.'
(Chen et al. 1986: 59)

111. **Guangka Palaung** 广卡德昂语 (Ruili, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

- (663) khrci⁵¹ **meh**⁵¹ te^{55?}i^{412/51}.
outside there.be person
'There's someone outside.'
(Ni 2007: 50)

Possessive frame

- (664) ?e^{412/55} tʃhi^{55/51} mɣ⁵⁵ ?u⁵⁵ **meh**⁵¹ ?u^{55?}
1PL who also NEG have Q
'Do none of us have (it)?'
(Ni 2007: 11-12)

Locative frame

(665) ?an^{51/55} **gɔi**^{412/51} pu⁵¹ khən^{412/51}tʃoŋ⁴¹².

3SG be.at still classroom

‘He’s still in the classroom.’

(Ni 2007: 21)

Copula

(666) ?an^{51/55} **moh**⁵¹ ?i⁵⁵phin⁵¹.

3SG COP Yiping_{NAME}

‘She’s Yiping.’

(Ni 2007:18)

112. **Stieng (Cambodia)**

Existential frame

(667) **?ən** təəm-tənuət bar təəm diəc da:k

there.be palm.tree two CLF.trunk near water

‘There are two palm trees near the water.’

Bon (2014: 377)

Possessive frame

(668) biəl hej ʔən luj ʔək hej han-məl digrɔŋ Pʰnom Bɛŋ.
time 1SG have money much 1SG visit town Phnom Penh
'When I get a lot of money, I'll visit Phnom Penh.'
(Bon 2014: 474)

(669) hej ʔən koən jəmət du:
1SG have child ten CLF.pers
'I have ten children.'
Bon (2014: 377)

Locative frame

(670) ni:h miŋ ja: ʔa waŋ Tɛ:h Dəm
house aunt be.at in village TD
'(My) aunt's house is in the village of TD' –Eli.
(Bon 2014: 357)

'live, stay'

(671) dʔuar-pəraŋ **ja:** kənoŋ ni:h sədiaŋ
 woman-French stay in house Stieng
 ‘The French woman stays in a Stieng style house.’ – Eli.
 (Bon 2014: 356)

Copula

Bon explains (2014: 376) that zero marking is the preferred strategy and she also points out that there is also a borrowed copula from Khmer, *ciə*, which corresponds to Stieng *ja:*. However, the example of *ja:* (Bon 2014: 376) does not entirely correspond to a copular construction under our framework. We only consider, thus, the zero marking as the strategy of forming a copular construction in Stieng.

(672) hej (nak sa:j) sədiaŋ
 1SG (person-bloodline) Stieng
 ‘I’m Stieng.’ –Eli.
 (Bon 2014: 376)

113. Pacoh (Vietnam)

Existential frame

(673) ŋɛʔ kər.rɔʔ ʔn.nɛh **vi:** ti.ko:l lam kər.rɔʔ ʔŋ.kan
 all cattle this exist eight UNIT cattle female

‘As for all these cattle here, there are eight cows.’

(Alves 2006: 103)

boon < ‘acquire’

(674) **boon** qaadùajh teq toom-qaalòòng trdii
there.is monkey LOC tree middle

‘There is a monkey in the middle of the tree.’

(Enfield 2003: 185)

Possessive frame

(675) mọ:j naʔ ti.kuəj **vi:** ba:r lam mat.
each UNIT person have two UNIT eye

‘Every person has two eyes.’

(Alves 2006: 44)

(676) qaadùajh lějq **boon** chòòj tòòj
monkey NEG have tail long

‘Monkey don’t have long tails.’

(Enfield 2003: 186)

(677) njèq naq **boon** mat baar paa
person which/any have eye two side
'Everyone has two eyes.'
(Enfield 2003: 186)

Locative frame

(678) dɔ: **ʔat** daŋ ʔŋ.koh
3s be.at place there
'He's over there.'
(Alves 2006: 105)

Copula: zero or the one borrowed from Vietnamese *là*.

(679) ʔn.nɛh **la:** krip
this LINK mousetrap
'As for this, it's a mousetrap.'
(Alves 2006: 40)

(680) ʔn.nɛh krip

this mousetrap

‘This is a mousetrap.’

(Alves 2006: 40)

114. **Blang** 布朗语 (Xinman’e, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(681) khaʔ⁴tuh² ɲaʔ² **kui²** khuʔ¹ ɭoŋ¹ kaʔ⁴ tiʔ⁴.

front house there.be tree tall CLF one

‘There’s a tall tree in front of the house.’

(Li et al. 1986: 64)

(682) **kui²** pɣi³ kaʔ⁴vaʔ² miʔ².

there.be person look.for you

‘There’s someone looking for you.’

(Li et al. 1986: 72)

Possessive frame

(683) ɣn¹ tuuk²tiʔ⁴ ɭoŋ¹, ɲei² un² **kui²** xeiŋ³ loh⁴.

3SG although tall but NEG have strength PRT

‘Although he’s tall, he doesn’t have strength.’

(Li et al. 1986: 71)

(684) taŋ⁴tɛ² kai⁴faŋ² khaŋ⁴niŋ¹, ɛŋ¹ koŋ⁴ **kui²** khuŋ⁴ tək²khuŋ⁴ tɕhup².
since liberation since 1PL then have NMLZ eat NMLZ wear

‘Since the liberation, we then have food and clothes.’

(Li et al. 1986: 45)

Locative frame

mok¹ ‘be at’

(Li et al. 1986: 114)

‘sit, live’

(685) tiŋ⁴ ɲ-**mok¹**

one VCLF-sit

‘sit for a while’

(Li et al. 1986: 38)

(686) pɛŋ¹ **mok¹** ʒuŋ¹ muŋ⁴?

2PL live village which
'Which village do you live?'
(Li et al. 1986: 73)

(687) ʔɿn³⁵ mok³⁵ man³¹muʔ³³?
3SG live where
'Which village do you live?'
(Zhou and Yan 1983: 79)

Copula

(688) ɿn¹ tɕuʔ⁴ pin¹ khuai⁴tɕi⁴, pin¹ tui²tɕaŋ².
3SG NEG COP bookkeeper COP teamleader
'He's not a bookkeeper but a team leader.'
(Li et al. 1986: 69)

115. Bugan 布赅语 (Wenshan, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(689) ti⁵⁵yo⁴⁴ kai⁴⁴ pjau²⁴
inside there.be person

‘There’s someone inside.’

(Li 2005: 292)

(690) ha⁵⁵ŋgu³¹ ɲdʒoŋ³¹ kai⁴⁴ mbei³¹ tsoŋ⁴⁴ su³¹.
front door there.be two CLF tree

‘There’re two trees in front of the door.’

(Li 2005: 215)

(691) kai⁴⁴ tsau⁴⁴ mbi⁴⁴ naŋ⁴⁴ kai⁴⁴ tu⁵⁵ qau⁴⁴tʂou⁴⁴.
there.be dog CLF sleep at middle road

‘There’s a dog sleeping in the middle of the road.’

(Li 2005: 206)

Possessive frame

(692) o³¹ kai⁴⁴ mu⁴⁴ tsen⁴⁴ nau⁴⁴ mboŋ³¹, tan²⁴ pi³¹ qou³¹thoŋ³¹.
1SG.NOM have one CLF shoe leather but not.have sock

‘I have a pair of leather shoes but I don’t have any socks.’

(Li 2005: 157)

Locative frame

(693) o³¹ kai⁴⁴ nei⁴⁴, mu³¹ kai⁴⁴ lo²⁴, xɔ³¹xɔ³¹da²⁴ phi³¹,
1SG.NOM be.at here 2SG.NOM be.at there well look DUR

no³¹ zaŋ²⁴ i³¹ qhei⁴⁴ a⁴⁴.
NEG.IMP let 3SG.NOM run PFV

‘I’m here; you are there; guard him well and don’t let him run away.’

(Li 2005: 225)

(694) sau⁴⁴ mu⁵⁵ kai⁴⁴ pau³¹ tɕoŋ⁴⁴ loŋ⁴⁴.
book 2SG.POSS be.at surface table upside

‘Your book is on the table.’

(Li 2005: 99)

‘live’

(695) o³¹ kai⁴⁴ tou⁴⁴mbjo⁴⁴ ɲou⁵⁵ i⁵⁵.
1SG.NOM live opposite.side home 3SG.POSS

‘I live across from his home.’

(Li 2005: 74)

Copula

(696) i³¹ ei²⁴ pɲau²⁴ ɲin⁴⁴ mbo⁴⁴.

3SG.NOM COP person bad CLF

‘He’s a bad person.’

(Li 2005: 199)

(697) i³¹ ɲou⁴⁴ pu³¹kui³¹ lou⁴⁴.

3SG.NOM COP craftman iron

‘He’s a blacksmith.’

(Li 2005: 193)

(698) pan⁴⁴ ɕo³¹ɕeŋ⁴⁴ nei⁴⁴, mu³¹ pha²⁴ tɕi⁴⁴ na⁴⁴pou⁴⁴, mu³¹ pha²⁴ tɕi⁴⁴ ɲa⁴⁴mou⁴⁴.

class student this one half COP boy one half COP girl

‘As for this class of students, half of them are boys and half of them are girls.’

(Li 2005: 220)

116. Mang 莽语 (Jinping, Yunnan, China)

Existential frame

(699) doŋ³¹ pan³¹ ʔe⁵¹ pɔp⁵⁵ lə³¹θə³⁵.
 CLF table there.be CLF book
 ‘There’s a book on the table.’
 (Gao 2002: 110)

Possessive frame

(700) lə³¹θə³¹ tak³⁵ ʔəm³¹ ʔe⁵¹, ʔəm³¹ tɕaŋ⁵¹ ʔɔ⁵¹ ʔa⁵⁵ʔu⁵⁵.
 but tongue NEG have NEG can speak speech
 ‘But (they) don’t have tongue and can’t speak.’
 (Gao 2002: 270)

Locative frame

(701) mə³¹tam³⁵ ʔe⁵⁵ ʔə³¹nam⁵¹ty⁵¹
 crab be.at high.place
 ‘The crab is up there.’
 (Gao 2002: 274)

(702) ʔə³¹tun³⁵ ʔe⁵¹ ʔə³¹ti³⁵ tə³¹ me³⁵.
 now be.at already at moon

‘Now, (he) is already on the moon.’

(Gao 2002: 272)

Locative preposition

(703) ʔa³¹ʔu⁵¹ ʔe⁵⁵ duɑŋ⁵¹do⁵¹ ʔəm³¹ tu⁵⁵ mək⁵⁵.

1SG at room NEG wear hat

‘I don’t wear a hat in the room.’

(Gao 2002: 90)

Copula

(704) mat⁵⁵ni³⁵ θə³¹ mə³¹ʔon³⁵, me³⁵ θə³¹ mə³¹tɕwa⁵¹.

sun COP male moon COP female

‘The sun is male, and the moon is female.’

(Gao 2002: 267)

(705) mə³¹ha⁵¹ ʔin³¹ pə³¹ tɕə⁵⁵ lau⁵⁵li³¹?

people this Q COP Mr. Li

‘Is this person Mr. Li?’

(Gao 2002: 114)

Note: the author uses both ʔe^{51} and ʔe^{51} to transcribe ‘have’, ‘there be’, ‘be at’ and ‘live’. See Y. Gao (2002: 251, 256).

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